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6G Goal-Oriented **AI**-enabled **L**earning and **S**emantic Communication Networks
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Deliverable D2.3

Reference system, scenarios, use-cases analysis and
requirements: final results

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Deliverable D2.3

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Abstract

This deliverable builds on previously submitted deliverables D2.1 and D2.2 and presents the final results from 6G-GOALS project for analysis and validation of reference systems, scenarios, use-cases, and requirements for 6G-oriented semantic and goal-oriented communications. Simulation results of the selected use-cases validate the feasibility and benefits of semantic communications in real-world scenarios. Meanwhile, driven by the paradigm shift in wireless networks towards AI-enabled, agile, and knowledge-driven architectures, this deliverable further discusses the reference system architecture encompassing semantic-aware radio access network (RAN), semantic-aware edge, and semantic-aware core network components, with four pivotal semantic management loops for performance monitoring, resource orchestration, model lifecycle management, knowledge base management, and energy efficiency. This deliverable further refines system design requirements and practical system-level considerations, paving the way for incorporation of semantic communications in 6G systems.

Keywords

6G, AI-native, use-cases validation, multimedia, task-oriented, semantic, network management, IoT, architecture, orchestration, goal-oriented, semantic management loops, knowledge base, SemComOps.

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation	Full Term
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5th Generation
6G	6th Generation
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
Aol	Age of Information
CA	Channel Attention
CQI	Channel Quality Indicator
CSI	Channel State Information
CoWu	Content-based Wake-Up Signals
Cobots	Collaborative Robotics
DKB	Distributed Knowledge Base
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DT	Digital Twin
DeepJSCC	Deep Joint Source and Channel Coding
GKB	Global Knowledge Base
GUIs	Graphical User Interfaces
IoT	Internet of Things
L1/L2	Layer 1 and Layer 2
LKB	Local Knowledge Base
LLMs	Large Language Models
LPWA	Low Power and Wide Access
M2M	Machine-to-Machine
MAC	Medium Access Control
MCS	Modulation and Coding Scheme
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multi-Input Multi-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MMSE	Minimum Mean Square Error
MOS	Mean Opinion Score
NOMA	Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access
OMA	Orthogonal Multiple Access
OSTBC	Orthogonal Space-Time Block Coding
PQ	Permanent Query
PSNR	Peak-Signal-Noise-Ratio
QAPA	Query Arrival Process Aware
QAol	Query Age of Information
QoE	Quality of Experience
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RISs	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
RR	Round-Robin

RU	Radio Unit
SESM	Semantic Edge Slicing Module
SDLA	Semantic Deep Learning Analyzer
SINR	Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio
SMO	Service Management and Orchestration
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SSRF	Semantic State Representation Function
SVR	Semantically Valid Responses
SemCom	Semantic Communication
SemComOps	Semantic Communication Operations
UE	User Equipment
UKB	User Knowledge Base
VAE	Variational Autoencoder
WP	Work Package
WuS	Wake-up Signal

1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives of this Deliverable

Building on the initial results shared in the deliverable D2.1 [6GGOALS-D21], this deliverable aims to present the final results of our analysis on the reference system, scenarios, use-cases, and requirements for 6G-oriented semantic and goal-oriented communications. We provide validation results for some of the use-cases selected from the taxonomical classification of use-cases, and offer a reference system design with practical considerations for the different network segments including semantic-aware radio access network (RAN), edge, and core network elements.

Another key aspect of this deliverable is the design of the semantic management loops which are expected to play a key role in the holistic management of: (1) system performance and in-network resource allocation and orchestration; (2) semantic model lifecycle; (3) semantic knowledge base; and (4) power consumption of the semantic functions.

This progression can be seen as a set of important evolution steps in wireless systems, where semantic features and goal-oriented strategies are embedded into the network architecture and real-world applications.

1.2 Overview of Deliverable D2.1 and D2.2

One important target of the 6G-GOALS project is to explore the theoretical underpinnings of semantic and goal-oriented communication and the feasibility of incorporating them into the 6G architecture. The 6G-GOALS project adopts a broad interpretation of “semantic” to include any structural, statistical, or causal relationships within the transmitted data, evaluated in the context of the desired outcomes at the receiver’s end. This, along with the concept of goal-oriented communications, underscore the necessity for 6G technologies to extract, process, and deliver the appropriate information at the right time to achieve specific objectives.

Semantic communication focuses on transmitting meaningful content that receivers can interpret in line with a shared understanding of concepts, while goal-oriented communication emphasizes using that meaningful information to achieve a specific, shared objective. In other words, the semantic exchange provides the interpretive framework, and the goal-oriented aspect ensures that these interpretations contribute toward a common goal.

For example, when transmitting an image over a wireless link, the information required varies depending on the receiver’s goal—be it a high-quality visual experience for a human user or essential features for an artificial intelligence (AI) enabled machine. This highlighted the need for adaptable communication strategies that align with diverse end use-cases.

The project aims to move beyond traditional communication paradigms towards AI-enabled architectures, protocols, and services that emphasize the pragmatic and judicious handling of information. Key innovations introduced in this project include:

- Redefining KPIs: shifting focus from traditional metrics like spectral efficiency to new measures assessing goal precision, learning capability, real-time operation, privacy, and data value, while considering energy efficiency trade-offs.
- AI-based communication technologies: designing wireless communication technologies that incorporate both semantic and pragmatic aspects of data for more intelligent and context-aware transmission.
- Intelligent RAN development: creating an adaptive RAN that controls L1/L2 functions with increasing complexity at the radio unit (RU) end.

- Adaptive bandwidth and spectrum usage: developing AI and machine learning (ML) technologies to support versatile spectrum usage and ensure coexistence between conventional and semantic communication systems.
- Sustainability focus: ensuring that 6G systems retain reliability, energy efficiency, and low electromagnetic field characteristics through mixed data-driven and model-based AI technologies.
- Proof-of-concept implementation: planning a field trial involving collaborative robots sharing semantic information to make collective decisions towards a common goal.

In the previously submitted deliverables ([6GGOALS-D21] and [6GGOALS-D22]), we presented the initial results of the reference system, scenarios, use-case analysis, and requirements, and defined the KPIs that are suitable for the evaluation of the semantic communication applications. In [6GGOALS-D21], we identified the relevant use-cases that can significantly benefit from semantic communication (SemCom), classified them into different categories, and provided a use-case taxonomy. Moreover, we proposed a taxonomy of system design requirements, in which we identified the 6G-GOALS system design requirements from the perspectives of architecture, function, management and orchestration, integration and compatibility, use-cases, and performance. For each requirement category, we listed the critical design considerations, aiming to contribute to the final system construction of 6G-GOALS.

D2.2 is dedicated to definition of specific KPIs/metrics. In that deliverable, we raised new KPIs/metrics that are applicable for semantic applications as well as the use-cases and demonstrate the linkages between these KPIs/metrics and the architecture design.

1.3 Advancements in This Deliverable

In this deliverable, we advance the groundwork laid in D2.1 and D2.2 by providing:

- Validation results for selected use-cases: We present simulation results that demonstrate the practical benefits and feasibility of semantic and goal-oriented communication in real-world scenarios. This includes performance evaluations and comparisons with traditional communication protocols.
- Detailed design of reference system: We provide a comprehensive system architecture from the perspective of semantic application management loops. These management loops lay the foundation for the fine-grained design of semantic network components and interfaces. Specifically, four pivotal management loops are elaborated in this deliverable:
 - Semantic application performance monitoring and in-network resource management and orchestration loop.
 - Semantic model's in-network lifecycle management loop.
 - Distributed and hierarchical semantic knowledge base management loop.
 - Energy consumption management loop.

1.4 Structure of This Document

The deliverable is organized as follows:

Section 2: validation of use-cases—this section details the methodology, implementation, and results of our validation efforts for the selected use-cases, demonstrating the advantages of semantic and goal-oriented communication.

Section 3: reference system design—here, we provide a reference system design that paves the way toward the envisioned 6G-GOALS system architecture design, building on the earlier identified system design requirements, and by exploiting the organic synergy of the edge, RAN,

and core network segments. We propose novel semantic management loops for realizing semantic awareness in wireless networks, aiming to realize semantic application-driven in-network resource allocation and orchestration, performance monitoring, semantic model lifecycle management, relevant knowledge base management, and energy consumption management.

Section 4: discussion—this section revisits the initial requirements, refining them based on validation results and providing a thorough analysis to guide future development. Additionally, we discuss practical aspects of implementing the system, such as scalability, interoperability, and maintenance, along with strategies to address potential challenges.

Section 5: conclusion—we conclude the deliverable with future work remarks.

2 Use-case Validation

This section presents the validation results for the SemCom use-cases, demonstrating the advantages of SemCom over traditional communication methods. Each use-case category from the taxonomy defined in [6GGOALS-D21] is represented by at least one selected use-case, which has been validated through preliminary simulations and/or emulations. The use-case categories include multimedia-centric use-cases, task-oriented use-cases, network management use-cases, and Internet of Things (IoT) use-cases.

2.1 Multimedia-centric Use-case

2.1.1 Deep joint source and channel coding for image transmission

Use-case description

In this subsection, the use-case will study the deep joint source and channel coding (DeepJSCC) to assist the image transmission over the multi-input multi-output (MIMO) Rayleigh fading channel. This use-case is described in [6GGOALS-D21], with the main relevant KPIs described in [6GGOALS-D22]. Instead of transmitting bit streams as in conventional way, we provide a specific image reconstruction implemented by DeepJSCC with goal of minimizing the pix-level distortion.

DeepJSCC is a communication technique that integrates both source and channel coding into a unified module using deep learning. This approach departs from traditional methods, which typically separate these two modules and leverages the power of neural networks to jointly encode and decode the information being transmitted across a noisy channel [EKG+19]. In the conventional approach, the separate source and channel coding is optimal if and only if at the infinite block length regime¹. However, the practical systems are limited to finite block lengths due to the limited channel resources and the limited channel coherence time. In contrast, the DeepJSCC technique has several advantages over the separate source and channel coding technique: 1) *graceful degradation*: Unlike the separate source and channel coding scheme that suffers from a "cliff effect" where the performance suddenly drops once the channel conditions worsen beyond a certain level, DeepJSCC offers graceful degradation without sharply failing; 2) *robust to channel noise*: Since the neural network is trained on noisy channels, it learns to incorporate redundancy into the latent representation in a way that optimizes error resilience; 3) *no separate error correction needed*: In the separate source and channel coding scheme, separate error correction codes are needed to handle noisy channels. In contrast, DeepJSCC requires end-to-end training over the noisy channel, inherently eliminating the need for complex error correction codes.

This use-case will use the DeepJSCC technique for efficient image transmission over MIMO fading channels, specifically under conditions where perfect channel state information (CSI) is available only at the receiver. Two distinct transmission strategies are proposed. The first approach, termed the *diversity scheme*, leverages orthogonal space-time block coding (OSTBC)

¹ The infinite block length regime refers to the data being transmitted or processed divided into blocks of infinite length.

to exploit the diversity gains offered by multiple transmit antennas. In this approach, the OSTBC encoder applies a non-linear transformation to the input image using a deep neural network (DNN) architecture to extract key features for image reconstruction. These features are then mapped onto the antennas and time slots based on the OSTBC structure for transmission. At the receiver, the signals are decoupled across the antennas to achieve full-time diversity, introducing redundancy that enhances robustness to channel variations. The second approach, referred to as the *multiplexing scheme*, directly maps the latent vector produced by the encoder to the antennas. At the receiver, the signal is recovered using the joint of the minimum mean square error (MMSE) equalizer and a residual neural network that utilizes the available CSI, followed by direct image reconstruction. This method is more general, as the DeepJSCC encoder-decoder pair, trained end-to-end, can inherently adapt to introduce redundancy when required (e.g., in low SNR conditions) to mitigate the effects of channel variability.

The primary objectives of this use-case are:

- To evaluate the impact of OSTBC on DeepJSCC for image transmission.
- To evaluate the impact of the multiplexing scheme on DeepJSCC for image transmission.
- To study the trade-off/relationship between diversity transmission and multiplexing transmission.
- To provide practical guidelines for designing efficient image transmission using different architectures.

2.1.1.1 Use-case Model

(a) Full diversity transmission.

(b) Multiplexing scheme.

Figure 2-1: The illustration of the diversity scheme and multiplexing scheme [CSW+23]

As shown in Figure 2-1, the system comprises 1) a transmitter with multiple antennas; 2) a receiver with multiple antennas; 3) a MIMO channel with Rayleigh fading; 4) a DeepJSCC encoder consisting of a series of neural networks; 5) a DeepJSCC decoder (OSTBC decoder and MMSE equalizer), which is also consisting of a series of neural networks; 6) two distinct transmission strategies for image transmission: full diversity transmission and multiplexing transmission; 7) Res network.

The detailed architecture of the DeepJSCC is shown in Figure 2-2. On the encoder side, it mainly consists of ResNet and channel attention (CA) modules. On the decoder side, it mainly

also comprises ResNet and CA modules, but upsample input features. Each module is described as follows.

Figure 2-2: The structure of the encoder, decoder, and the residual block [CSW+23]

Encoder:

The Encoder is composed of the following main modules:

- **ResNet Module:** The ResNet architecture helps capture important image features while minimizing the complexity of the network.
- **CA Module:** This module within the encoder takes features, signal power, and noise power as inputs. The CA module dynamically adjusts feature extraction to optimize for different SNR conditions, enhancing robustness under varying channel conditions.
- **Linear and LeakyReLU Layers:** The encoder further applies linear transformations and LeakyReLU activation functions to the image features, refining the feature extraction process.
- **Power Norm Layer:** This layer is designed to normalize the power of the latent vector before transmission, ensuring that the transmitted signal adheres to a specific power constraint.

Decoder:

Similar to the encoder, the decoder also includes ResNet and CA modules to adapt to varying SNRs, ensuring accurate reconstruction under different conditions. It uses a structure where pixel shuffling is implemented within some ResNet modules, which is useful for upscaling the input features to the original image dimensions. This process allows the system to maintain high image quality after reconstruction.

Residual Block for MIMO Equalization (Res Layer):

This layer is part of the receiver's structure for estimating the transmitted latent vector by addressing errors from channel distortions. The Res Layer takes in both the received signal and the CSI to refine the estimation of the transmitted signal. This improves the accuracy of the latent vector before it is fed into the decoder. In the following, we provide the details on the full diversity scheme and multiplexing scheme.

Full diversity scheme

In this scheme, the transmitter applies a space-time coding scheme to achieve diversity gain.

- **Objective:** The primary goal of the full diversity scheme is to exploit the multiple antennas at the transmitter to send the same data in a way that maximizes the probability of correct reception, even when individual channels experience deep fades. This is achieved by using OSTBC.

- **OSTBC:** OSTBC encodes the output of the DeepJSCC encoder into a matrix format that can be transmitted over multiple antennas and time slots. This coding technique ensures that the transmitted signals are orthogonal, which helps achieve full diversity gain.
- **Advantage:** This scheme is particularly beneficial in low SNR conditions where robustness to channel variations is critical.

For better clarity, this scheme adopts a classic OSTBC scheme, namely the Alamouti scheme [A98], for two antennas. In the encoding process, it mainly includes two stages:

- **Latent Vector Partitioning:** The latent vector is divided into two tuples used for two transmit antennas.
- **OSTBC Mapping:** Each tuple of the latent vector is mapped into a space-time block across two antennas and two time slots.

The receiver can linearly combine the received signals, and a simple linear MMSE estimator can be applied to decode the transmitted signals directly by considering the fact that the OSTBC matrix is orthogonal.

Multiplexing scheme

The multiplexing scheme leverages multiple transmit antennas to send distinct parts of the data simultaneously, rather than prioritizing redundancy as in the full diversity scheme.

- **Objective:** The multiplexing scheme aims to increase the amount of data transmitted per channel use by mapping different segments of the output of the DeepJSCC encoder directly onto the antennas without introducing redundancy.
- **Advantage:** This scheme is especially beneficial in high SNR conditions, where reliability is less of a concern, allowing the focus to shift toward maximizing throughput.

On the transmit side, the encoder produces a latent vector representing the essential features of the input image, which is then directly mapped to a matrix across the antennas without applying space-time code like in the diversity scheme. After passing through the wireless channel, the receiver first applies a linear MMSE equalizer to estimate the transmitted signals. To mitigate/reduce the estimation error caused by the noise, a residual connection layer (Res Layer) is applied to improve the accuracy of the MMSE estimate.

2.1.1.2 Results and discussion

The simulation is provided to show the efficient schemes for image transmission. The system setup is given as follows: we adopt CIFAR-10 dataset with 50000 training colour images and 10000 testing images. For the Res layer, it has 128 hidden neurons.

In Figure 2-3, we study peak-signal-noise-ratio (PSNR) versus SNR with number of transmit antennas $N_t = 2$ and bandwidth ratio $1/8$ for different numbers of receive antennas N_r . It can be observed that when $N_r = 1$, the diversity scheme significantly outperforms the multiplexing scheme, even in high SNR conditions. For $N_r = 2$, the multiplexing scheme surpasses the diversity scheme when the SNR exceeds 16 dB. When $N_r = 4$, the multiplexing scheme consistently outperforms the diversity scheme across all SNR levels. The reason is that at low SNR, the diversity scheme is advantageous because it enhances transmission reliability. However, as the SNR increases, and reliability becomes less of a concern, exploiting the available antennas for multiplexing becomes more advantageous, as it reduces end-to-end distortion.

In Figure 2-4, we study PSNR versus SNR with $N_t = 3, N_r = 1$ for different bandwidth ratios. It can be observed that when $\rho = 1/8$, even in the low SNR regime, both diversity schemes outperform the multiplexing scheme. This is primarily due to the low OSTBC rate for $N_t \geq 3$, which limits the system's ability to effectively convey the image data. Consequently, it is more advantageous to leverage the available antennas for multiplexing gain. Notably, with $\kappa = 384$ MIMO channel uses $\rho = 1/8$, the length l of the latent vector for the multiplexing scheme is 1152,

whereas for the rate-1/2 and rate-3/4 OSTBC schemes, l is 192 and 288, respectively, which are insufficient to achieve high-quality reconstruction.

Figure 2-3: PSNR versus SNR under different numbers of receive antennas [CSW+23]

Figure 2-4: PSNR versus SNR under different bandwidth ratios [CSW+23]

However, as the bandwidth ratio increases to $\rho = 5/24$, both diversity schemes exhibit comparable or superior performance to the multiplexing scheme as l becomes larger. Additionally, it is observed that the rate-1/2 OSTBC performs better than the rate-3/4 at lower SNR values, which is expected as the rate-1/2 code offers a higher coding gain and thus greater reliability. Although OSTBC provides full diversity, the reduced bandwidth limits its overall end-to-end reconstruction performance when $N_r \geq 1$.

2.1.1.3 Recommendations for system design

Integrating DeepJSCC-MIMO into L1/L2 layers involves rethinking these foundational aspects of the network to incorporate deep learning models that perform both source and channel coding

jointly. First, the DeepJSCC encoder and DeepJSCC decoder are trained in a centralized way so that all the information at the encoder and decoder sides should be known by the semantic RIC; then, the semantic RIC should carefully coordinate the forward propagation and backpropagation, enabling neural parameters update efficiently. Second, feeding the channel state information to both the encoder and decoder in the DeepJSCC-MIMO scheme allows for a more integrated and adaptive approach to handling communications, particularly image transmissions in wireless environments. This leads to better utilization of channel resources, improved robustness against errors, and overall enhanced performance compared to traditional methods. Thus, the channel state information should be estimated first in the physical layer and then the Semantic RIC needs to consider feeding the estimated channel state information into both encoder and decoder.

2.2 Task-oriented Use-case

2.2.1 Multi-robot system for anomaly detection

2.2.1.1 Use-case description

The integration of advanced collaborative robotics (cobots) and communication technologies offers new solutions for industrial monitoring and surveillance systems, wherein robots are increasingly deployed to perform tasks such as equipment inspection, anomaly detection, and data collection, either working in collaborative manner or operating individually. In the indoor environment, these robots navigate complex terrains, identify potential issues, and communicate critical information mutually or back to a central processing unit or control centre for further processing.

The operation of cobot systems is underpinned by various challenges, such as synchronization of the robot nodes, task allocation and cooperation, and communication overheads. Among these, the communication overhead raises particular interest for the communication community, considering frequent information exchange in a multi-robot system. Traditional communication methods often involve transmitting raw sensor data, which can consume a large portion of the available system bandwidth leading to network congestion and potential performance degradation, as well as increased energy consumption on the robot device. Therefore, the question is, how to develop new communication paradigm for cobots to reduce the communication overhead while retaining the quality and semantic of the transmitted information, to enable a more efficient transmission of data between the robots and the central processor (or other robot nodes), especially in environments where bandwidth is limited, communication channels are noisy, or latency must be minimized.

SemCom emerges as a promising solution to address this challenge. As stated in previous sections, unlike conventional communication systems that focus on transmitting exact data, SemCom prioritizes the transmission of the meaning or essential information contained within the data. By encoding and transmitting only the semantic content thereby contained, it is possible to reduce the amount of data that needs to be shared, thereby improving communication efficiency without significantly compromising the integrity of the information.

In this use-case, we demonstrate how SemCom can contribute to the operation of cobot and reduce the communication overhead in a robotic surveillance scenario within an industrial environment. Specifically, in this preliminary simulation evaluation we explore the compression capability of SemCom. We assume each robot is equipped with a variational autoencoder (VAE)-based semantic encoder for the image compression, while the central server is equipped with the decoder sector of the VAE for the image reconstruction. The primary objectives of this use-case are:

- To evaluate the impact of SemCom on wireless traffic reduction.
- To assess the effect of semantic compression on the accuracy of device classification.

- To compare the performance of the system with and without SemCom.
- To provide insights and recommendations for designing efficient robotic monitoring systems leveraging semantic communication.

2.2.1.2 Use-case Model

The simulation considers an industrial environment measuring 100 meters by 100 meters. The environment is populated with industrial devices that require monitoring. These devices in simulation are represented by images from the MNIST dataset, which consists of handwritten digits from 0 to 9. The devices are classified as:

- **Abnormal Devices:** Represented by images of even digits (0, 2, 4, 6, 8). These devices signify equipment that may be malfunctioning or require maintenance.
- **Normal Devices:** Represented by images of odd digits (1, 3, 5, 7, 9). These devices are functioning correctly.

Obstacles, modelled as walls in this simulation, are strategically placed within the environment to create a realistic and challenging navigation scenario for the robots. The walls are defined by their positions and dimensions, forming barriers that the robots must navigate around.

2.2.1.3

Robotic Agents

Five autonomous robots are deployed in the environment with the following capabilities:

- **Sensors:** Each robot is equipped with a camera capable of capturing images of devices within a 2-meter radius field of view.
- **Navigation:** Robots use the A* path planning algorithm [HNB+68] to navigate towards assigned target devices while avoiding obstacles.
- **Communication:** Robots have the ability to transmit data back to the central processor over a wireless communication channel through a 5G dongle.

Communication Framework

The communication between the robots and the central server is designed to reflect realistic wireless communication constraints and incorporates SemCom principles. For the design of the semantic encoder and decoder, we employ the VAE architecture, semantic encoder is deployed on the robots and the decoder deployed at the central processor. The encoder compresses the 28x28 pixel images into a 20-dimensional latent space vector, capturing the essential compressed features of the images; while the decoder reconstructs the images from the latent vectors received at the central processor.

We used the 3GPP indoor channel model [3GPP38.901] between the robots and the wireless access point server for the modelling of the communication channel, and the single input and single output (SISO) wireless communication systems are assumed in the robot node and central sever access point This allows the simulation to calculate the path loss based on the distance between each robot and the central server, providing a realistic estimation of the received signal strength. Using this signal strength, the simulation code computes the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) and maps it to a channel quality indicator (CQI). The CQI is then used to select the appropriate modulation and coding scheme (MCS) for data transmission between the robots and the central server.

By adapting the MCS based on the channel conditions, the simulation can accurately calculate the achievable data rate and the time required to transmit data from the robots to the central server, in a more realistic and detailed manner. That enhances the fidelity of the simulation and enables better analysis of network performance. In this simulation, the amount of data transmitted is calculated based on the size of the modulated data, allowing for the assessment of wireless traffic generated during the simulation.

Operational Scenarios

Two operational branches are modelled to evaluate the impact of SemCom. Branch A: SemCom is enabled, wherein robots use the VAE encoder to compress images into 20-dimensional latent vectors before transmission. This could reduce data size transmitted, leading to decreased wireless traffic and bandwidth usage. Branch B: SemCom is disabled, i.e., robots transmit raw images without any compression as no compression is employed.

Central Server Functions

A central processor is assumed in the simulation, which performs several critical functions. (1) data reception and reconstruction (if applicable). When the Branch A is used in simulation, the central processor will demodulate received data and uses the VAE decoder to reconstruct images from latent vectors, while when Branch B is used, it demodulates received data and processes raw images directly. After receiving or reconstructing the raw image, the central processor will conduct the classification function, to utilize a pre-trained MNIST classifier to identify the digits in the images. It will classify devices as normal or abnormal based on the identified digits.

Meanwhile, this central processor is responsible for the task assignment of all the robot nodes, it will assign robots to undetected devices based on proximity and robot availability and ensure efficient coverage of the environment and optimal utilization of robotic resources.

Simulation Parameters

- The simulation parameters are listed as follows:
- Total simulation time: 400 seconds, with time steps of 1 second.
- Robot field of view: 2 meters radius for device detection.
- Robot speed: 2 meters per second².
- Data measurement: wireless traffic is measured in megabits (Mb) transmitted during the simulation.

2.2.1.4 Results and discussion

The simulation tracked the total amount of data transmitted from the robots to the central processor in both operational branches. The simulation process, including the robot nodes locations, indoor layout and robot moving trajectory, is shown in Figure 2-5, and the detailed image that robot observed, transmitted and centre server reconstructed during the simulation process is displayed in Figure 2-6.

In Branch A of this simulation, when SemCom is enabled, the data transmitted per image is determined by the latent vector size, which is 20 floating-point numbers. The data size per image is approximately 0.64 kb (assuming 32 bits per floating-point number). We considered 20 devices for detection in this simulation, so the total data transmitted is approximately 12.8 kb. In Branch B, when SemCom is disabled, the data transmitted per image is actually the raw image data which is 784 (28 x 28) pixels. So, the data size per image is approximately 25.09 kb. Similarly, with 20 devices detected, the total data transmitted is approximately 501.8 kb.

These results show that the VAE successfully preserved the semantic content necessary for accurate digit recognition. Branch A achieved a data reduction of approximately 97% compared to Branch B. The significant reduction in data transmission underscores the effectiveness of semantic communication in optimizing network resources.

Moreover, Branch A achieved significant bandwidth savings, although the fidelity of the image slightly reduced due to compression but maintained acceptable levels of accuracy. Branch B consumed more bandwidth, which may not be sustainable in constrained networks. Meanwhile, Branch A reduces the network load, enhancing system scalability and reliability and lower data volumes in Branch A enable faster data transmission and processing, which is critical for real-time monitoring applications.

² To simplify the simulation, the Doppler effect caused by the robot's movement is not taken into account.

Figure 2-5: The simulation process of cobot, showing the positions of the robot nodes and their trajectories at simulation time 0s (a) and time 117s (b). In this process, robots are assigned via a central node to inspect the operational status of various devices until all devices have been thoroughly checked.

Figure 2-6: Shows the images that robot observed, transmitted and centre server reconstructed during the simulation process.

The use-case analysis demonstrates that SemCom, implemented through VAE, offers significant advantages in robotic monitoring systems. By effectively compressing data and transmitting only the essential semantic information, it is possible to reduce wireless traffic dramatically without substantially compromising the accuracy of device classification.

The adoption of semantic communication aligns with the growing need for efficient, scalable, and intelligent industrial systems. As industrial environments become more connected and data-driven, the ability to optimize communication processes will be critical to maintaining system performance and reliability.

2.2.1.5 Recommendations

The successful implementation of the cobot use-case depends on seamless interaction between robot nodes and a central server, as well as effective coordination among the nodes themselves. The RIC is well-suited to serve as the central orchestrator, enabling efficient communication and coordination among devices. In the context of SemCom, equipping the RIC with semantic-awareness capabilities is crucial, emphasizing the need for a semantic-RIC. This semantic-RIC can host microservices for semantic information reconstruction and cobot control policy execution. Simultaneously, robot nodes leverage the on-board computational devices' semantic processing capabilities to interpret semantic information and execute actions accordingly.

To effectively support the cobot use-case, the system design should prioritize semantic-awareness across network components. The RIC should act as a centralized orchestrator, hosting microservices for semantic information reconstruction and cobot coordination, while cobot nodes should integrate lightweight semantic processing capabilities for decentralized, low-latency decision-making. Continuous monitoring and lifecycle management of semantic models are critical, supported by a robust SemComOps pipeline to maintain long-term reliability and efficiency. Additionally, the system should include mechanisms for semantic error detection and resilience against adversarial attacks while ensuring scalability, energy efficiency, and real-time adaptability to dynamic operational contexts. These measures collectively enhance the robustness, efficiency, and responsiveness of the goal-oriented and semantic-aware network design.

2.2.2 Edge inference use-case

General use-case description

The edge inference use-case is preliminarily described in [6GGOALS-D21], with the main relevant KPIs described in [6GGOALS-D22]. The general idea is to exploit distributed computation resources at the edge of wireless networks to enable ML/AI-based methods for fast decision-making, data interpretation, detection, classification. The proximity of computing resources to the data source makes it extremely convenient from a latency perspective, privacy preserving and backbone network load reduction. When it comes to energy consumption, intelligent decisions must be taken on where and when to place an AI/ML-related workload, based on current traffic conditions, battery lifetime, energy mix, latency constraints, and performance of the inference task running at the edge (e.g., classification, object detection, image reconstruction, etc.).

The edge inference use-case has implications for the SemCom framework at different levels:

1. At the physical layer, with DJSCC techniques, thus mostly related to the semantics underlying data with a link-level perspective; this also involves the application layer with source coding [GWT+24].
2. Still at the physical layer, for transmitter/receiver precoding and decoding, power control, but also for the reconfiguration of intelligent surfaces able to shape the channel response based on the specific goal of communication [GY22].
3. At higher layers, such as MAC for resource orchestration, including workload placement, splitting user association to radio and computing resources [PKC+24], [BMB+24], [MFG+24], [ZWL+23].

The problem can thus be tackled at the link level, with an optimised point-to-point communication, or at system level, with multiple users willing to achieve target performance and competing for radio and computing resources. While the former is the focus of WP3 and WP4, the network level is mostly investigated in WP5, with fairness in resource sharing also playing a key role. Typical KPIs include inference accuracy, latency, throughput, bandwidth usage and energy efficiency, with the latter going beyond classical definitions based on the energy spent per transmitted bit, towards the concept of energy per goal [6GGOALS-D21], [6GGOALS-D22] rather

than the classical measure of energy per bit. Obviously, a combination of both with an end-to-end system optimisation is the most complete and desirable solution.

In the following, the general use-case model will be presented. Then, three examples are proposed at physical, and application layers (including workload placement). Therefore, each example will come with the specific scenario and model description.

General Use-case Model

In Figure 2-7, we show the most general scenario, with a set of heterogeneous agents embarked with more or less computing resources, interacting with the environment, collecting data, processing them, and possibly offloading part of the computation to nearby edge servers. The latter are able to take over computation for either better performance or to relieve the former from too heavy workloads, thus possibly increasing their battery lifetime, among other things. In such a system, several entities belonging to different layers play a role: i) end devices, collecting data, possibly pre-processing, and sharing with the infrastructure, ii) wireless access points, receiving data and routing them to selected iii) edge servers, processing data or intermediate results and providing final results and/or decisions, iv) Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) helping communication in case of coverage holes or blockages. All these entities play a role in the edge inference process, depending on user needs, energy and resource availability, coverage, etc.

Figure 2-7: General system model for edge inference: physical layer and network optimization

In the most general case, once an edge computing unit is selected (for example co-located with a wireless access point), the edge inference process involves the following steps:

1. Sensing/collecting data (e.g., a camera taking images)
2. Local processing (e.g., for feature extraction)
3. Transmission of intermediate results
4. Remote processing
5. Transmission of results

Depending on the scenario and/or instantaneous network conditions, some of the above steps could be skipped. For instance, the results could be needed only at the receiver, so the transmission of results becomes useless/redundant. Each of these steps increases the delay, which depends on availability of computing (local and remote) and communication resources. One can

refer to as the entire delay (from data generation/sensing to result computation) as loop delay, as defined in [6GGOALS-D22]. All intermediate steps of the loop delay are described in Table 2-1, along with their notation and a set of parameters affecting each one of them.

Similarly, as for the loop delay, a loop energy can be defined. However, the energy KPI can also be split between local energy (for the end device) and remote energy (for the network), due to, e.g., the heterogeneous energy availability and possibly also different orders of magnitude. In fact, while the network (wireless and edge computing) can rely on the energy from the grid, resource poor devices are usually powered by batteries, whose capacity should be taken into account in system optimisation. However, network energy is also a fundamental metric to assess the impact of a service [MBR+23].

In the following, we present three examples, along with first simulation results illustrating the benefit of the semantic and goal-oriented communication approach over conventional schemes: the first one is representative of source coding and physical layer optimisation with semantic communication for image reconstruction via collaborative inference with deep joint source and channel coding; the second one presents a novel method for edge image classification via adaptive token selection using visual transformers; finally, the third one related to goal-aware workload placement through the concept of DNN splitting.

Table 2-1: Loop delay: sources and impacting system parameters

Loop delay					
Type	Sensing	Local computation	Intermediate result transmission (uplink)	Remote computation	Result transmission (downlink)
Notation	T_s	$T_{c,l}$	$T_{tx,u}$	$T_{c,r}$	$T_{tx,d}$
Variables impacting the delay source	sampling frequency	Local comp. resources	Intermediate feature map size	Remote computing resources	Downlink bandwidth
	resolution	Number/depth of local computations	Bandwidth	Number/depth of local computations	Size of results
		Local energy needs	Modulation and coding scheme (or, bandwidth ratio for DJSCC techniques)	Number/depth of remote computations	Number of served users
		Secrecy needs	Transmit power		
			Number of served users		

Scenario 1: Collaborative Semantic Communication for Edge Inference

2.2.2.1 Description

The edge inference use-case is described in [6GGOALS-D21], with the main relevant KPIs described in [6GGOALS-D22]. This edge inference use-case considers the collaborative image retrieval problem, which involves multiple edge devices (e.g., cameras) that capture images of the same object from different perspectives. These devices then transmit the images or extracted features over a shared wireless channel to a central server, which retrieves similar images from a gallery database. The gallery database on this server is used to retrieve similar

images or relevant data. This approach allows for the leveraging of collaborative information from various sources, enhancing the accuracy of image retrieval by providing a more comprehensive view of the object. This collaborative approach is particularly useful in scenarios where individual images may lack certain details or perspectives, and combining multiple viewpoints improves the retrieval accuracy.

The primary objectives of the image edge inference case are:

- To improve the accuracy of identifying and retrieving images by leveraging multiple perspectives captured by different devices, which together provide a richer and more complete representation of the object.
- To optimize the use of limited bandwidth by focusing on transmitting semantic features rather than full images, ensuring that key information is shared without overloading the communication channel.
- To evaluate whether the JSCC can guarantee reliable transmission and retrieval performance under various channel conditions.

Figure 2-8: Illustration of image retrieval problem at the wireless edge [WWG+23]

2.2.2.2 Model

As shown in Figure 2-8, the illustration of the two-device collaborative image retrieval at the wireless edge is plotted. The two cameras (i.e., edge devices) capture images of the same object or scene from different angles or perspectives. Then, the two cameras transmit their semantic features over a shared wireless channel to an edge server, which performs an image retrieval task based on a gallery database by adopting the loss function: cross-entropy losses between the identity prediction result from each classifier plus entropies of the quantized semantic feature.

Instead of using the conventional separate source and channel coding, the JSCC approach is adopted. In this use-case, two JSCC schemes are considered:

- **DeepJSCC with orthogonal multiple access (OMA):** Two edge devices employing time division multiple access to transmit their semantic information independently to the edge server.
- **DeepJSCC with non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA):** Each transmitter occupies the full channel bandwidth and transmits the data at the same time. This approach leverages the superposition property of the wireless medium and advanced joint decoding at the edge server to handle the combined signal, making it particularly effective in high SNR environments.

The JSCC-based transmission pipeline architecture is given in Figure 2-9, where it mainly consists of a semantic encoder, JSCC encoder, JSCC decoder, view-pooling, and auxiliary classifier. Each module is described as follows:

Figure 2-9: Transmission pipeline for the JSCC [WWG+23]

- **Semantic encoder:** Each image passes through a semantic encoder that extracts the key features of the image, reducing its dimensionality. This encoder is typically a convolutional neural network and produces a feature vector that represents the most relevant content of the image for retrieval.
- **JSCC encoder:** It takes the feature vector from the feature encoder and maps it to a channel symbol representation suitable for wireless transmission at the transmitter. This encoding is designed to combine both compression and error-resilience properties, directly mapping the feature vector into a form that can withstand the noisy channel. The modules in the JSCC encoder are depicted in Figure 2-10. It consists of several fully connected layers, batch normalization layers, and a Leaky ReLU layers.
- **JSCC Decoder:** At the receiver, the JSCC decoder decodes the received signals and reconstructs the feature vectors for each image. This decoder is trained to interpret the received signal and recover the transmitted semantic features while compensating for channel distortions. This module in the JSCC decoder is similar to that in the JSCC encoder depicted in Figure 2-10. It also consists of several fully connected layers, batch normalization layers, and Leaky ReLU layers.

Figure 2-10: DNN architecture for the JSCC transmission schemes [WWG+23]

- **View-Pooling Layer:** It combines the features from both transmitters, allowing the system to make the best use of the information from both perspectives, particularly for common or overlapping features of the object. This step enhances the retrieval accuracy by merging the complementary viewpoints into a single representation for comparison.
- **Image Retrieval Module:** This module seeks to match the combined features to entries in a gallery database.

2.2.2.3 Results and discussion

The simulation results are provided to evaluate the performance of edge image inference by the proposed JSCC scheme. The simulation parameters are listed as follows:

- **Dataset:** The simulation adopts the Market-1501 dataset.
- **Channel:** Two types of channels are adopted, namely, Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) and Rayleigh fading channel.
- **Channel bandwidth:** Two channel uses are adopted, namely, 32 or 64.

Figure 2-11 shows the Top-1 accuracy versus channel SNR for different channel types, specifically AWGN and Rayleigh fading channels. Here, the "top-1 accuracy" refers to the metric used to measure the accuracy of a model in identifying the correct answer as its first choice. In Figure 2-11(a), Top-1 accuracy is examined against channel SNR under an AWGN channel. Figure 2-11(b) focuses on Top-1 accuracy versus channel SNR under a Rayleigh fading channel without CSI at the receiver, while Figure 2-11(c) examines Top-1 accuracy for a Rayleigh fading channel with CSI available at the receiver.

The results indicate that the proposed JSCC scheme outperforms the separate digital scheme across nearly all SNRs, with the exception of high SNR levels. Additionally, the two-device JSCC scheme demonstrates superior performance compared to the single-device JSCC scheme over a broad range of SNRs, particularly at higher SNRs. This improvement highlights that using two views of the same identity to make collaborative decisions at the edge server enhances retrieval accuracy. Furthermore, it is also evident that JSCC with NOMA outperforms its orthogonal counterpart.

Figure 2-11: Top-1 retrieval accuracies of the proposed JSCC schemes under different channel SNRs, with a total channel bandwidth of channel uses 64 [WWG+23]

In Figure 2-12(a), the effect of correlation between transmitted signals on the performance of the NOMA-JSCC scheme is studied. The results show that the accuracy declines as the correlation between the signals decreases. Notably, as cosine similarity in the NOMA scheme approaches zero, its accuracy converges to that of the OMA scheme. In Figure 2-12(b) and (c), the SNR-awareness of the two JSCC schemes are compared with non-SNR-aware architectures that are trained at a specific SNR but tested across various SNR levels. It is observed that the non-SNR-aware JSCC architectures degrade gradually when there is a channel mismatch, specifically when test conditions are worse than training conditions.

This gradual degradation allows the JSCC scheme to avoid the "cliff effect" commonly appeared in conventional digital communication, where performance drops sharply when channel quality decreases below a threshold. The SNR-aware JSCC architectures demonstrate consistently higher retrieval accuracy than their non-SNR-aware counterparts, see Figure 2-12(b) and Figure 2-12(c), offering a single DNN that performs as well or better across all SNRs, eliminating the need for multiple DNNs optimized for specific SNR ranges.

Figure 2-12: Impact of correlation and channel models on Top-1 accuracy [WWG+23]

Scenario 2: Adaptive token selection for edge image classification

2.2.2.4 Description and model

The DJSCC concept can be realised in several ways, including more powerful architectures including visual transformers, which can be opportunistically optimised for wireless communication, adapting to channel bandwidth constraints. Starting from the extraction of tokens by the transformer model, the idea is to select only a subset of semantically relevant tokens to be transmitted over wireless, with a tunable budget parameter that trades off accuracy and bandwidth. Moreover, the bandwidth parameter also affects the computational burden of the transformer, thus reducing the complexity with respect to the base architecture. Thus, a method is proposed to adaptively select tokens based on the selected budget.

A visual example of the proposed architecture is illustrated in Figure 2-13, with the token selection blocks before each transformer block, as well as before the wireless channel transmission block, which is modelled as a set of non-trainable layers. The model is trained end-to-end with randomly selected budgets during different epochs, while a given budget is selected during inference to explore the trade-off between accuracy, complexity and amount of data to transmit over wireless. Further details are available in [DPP+24].

Figure 2-13: token selection blocks in the transformer architecture, to adaptively reduce the burden on computation and wireless channel (this figure is from [DPP+24])

2.2.2.5 Results and discussion

Here, first results assessing the performance of the proposed method are presented and compared with a benchmark scheme. The proposed scheme is trained and tested on an AWGN channel, with different SNR values, and different budgets. Instead, the benchmark scheme considers a digital communication of JPEG images, with source coding rate selected to match the wireless channel capacity, and by considering a reliable communication without errors, as in [BBG19]. Namely, given a source of size n , the maximum number of bits that can be reliably transmitted on the channel is $R_{\max} = \frac{k}{n} \log_2(1 + \text{SNR})$, with $\frac{k}{n}$ the compression ratio. Therefore, for the JPEG case, as in [BBG19], for a given $\frac{k}{n}$ and SNR, we compress the image using the minimum compression ratio that meets the constraint. If no compression is able to meet the constraint, the data sample is automatically considered as not correctly classified, as it cannot be received and reconstructed reliably. The solution is tested on image classification on the Imagenette dataset. Figure 2-14(a)-(g) show the accuracy as a function of the compression ratio $\frac{k}{n}$, for different SNR values ranging from -15 dB to 20 dB.

Figure 2-14: accuracy-compression ratio trade-off with adaptive token selection with vision transformer and digital transmission with JPEG compression

It should be noted that, for JPEG, a sample that is not possible to classify under the channel capacity constraint is considered as not being correctly classified. As one can notice, there is a clear advantage in using the vision transformer with the adaptive token selection, especially in low SNR regimes, in which the digital scheme fails due to the impossibility of reconstructing the image to be classified. Obviously, by increasing the SNR, the digital scheme also exhibits very good performance in terms of trade-off between accuracy and compression ratio. These results show the promising benefits of adopting an end-to-end training and inference solution that directly map the features to complex symbols, via a series of transformations that promote great robustness to channel noise. Future work should include testing over fading channels, but also techniques to further reduce the number of channel symbols k , given the stable behaviour of the accuracy when adopting the proposed solution.

Scenario 3: Adaptive goal-aware DNN splitting point selection

2.2.2.6 Description and model

DNN splitting is a powerful concept in wireless scenarios, where the availability and quality of radio and computing resources varies over time, thus demanding for a continuous adaptation of workload placement and sharing among end devices collecting data, and edge servers offering computing resources as a service. In fact, through DNN splitting, part of the workload can be taken by the end device for several reasons: i) reduce the size of the payload transmitted over wireless; ii) overcome current unavailability of computing resources at the edge, due to the sharing with other (possibly higher priority) services; iii) achieve higher robustness to noise. As an example, Figure 2-15(a) shows the size of the output feature map and the number of MAC operations to be performed locally, as a function of the splitting point (SP) choice, for the Mobilenetv2 model [SHZ18], [LMA+23]. To complement, Figure 2-15(b) shows the accuracy achieved by the model as a function of the SP index, meaning that offloading takes place afterwards. The latter is shown for different SNR values, and clearly highlights an increasing behaviour of the accuracy with respect to the depth of local computations. The architecture is tested on the Intel-Scene classification dataset [Ban19].

Figure 2-15: Output feature map size & local computing burden (a) [LMA+23] and accuracy (b) [BMB+24] as functions of splitting point selection for the Mobilenetv2 architecture

Under these observations, it is clear that the trade-off between local computation burden (i.e., energy consumption and delay), communication resource usage (i.e., bandwidth, energy and delay), and remote computation (i.e., energy and delay), and accuracy, strongly depends on the

SP choice, with the latter being dynamic and depending on (time-varying) local and remote computing resources, but also wireless channel conditions.

Thus, the decision making should be aware of the goal of communication. In the studied case it involves: i) the SP, ii) bandwidth, iii) transmit power, and iv) local CPU cycle frequency for computation (with energy growing quadratically with the latter [BMB+24]). The availability of remote computing resources is assumed to be an exogenous variable that depends on the presence of other services. As such, the remote computing delay $T_{c,r}$ is a random variable that cannot be controlled, with the end device required to accordingly select the SP to achieve the desired performance. The latter is represented by the loop delay (from data generation to result output), and obviously by the accuracy. In this case, we consider $T_{c,l}$, $T_{tx,u}$, $T_{c,r}$ in the computation of the loop delay. For further details on problem formulation and solution, the reader is referred to [BMB+24].

2.2.2.7 Results and discussion

As a candidate result, Figure 2-16 shows the energy saving achieved by offloading computation from the end device to the edge server, as a function of the accuracy loss with respect to full local computation (i.e., without wireless communication) for two different schemes: i) full offloading, i.e., the raw images are transmitted, and ii) the proposed method with goal-aware SP selection. The full offloading case is tested under two average channel conditions, namely path-loss 100 dB and 105 dB, while the proposed method with the 105 dB pathloss, i.e., the worst condition among the two. As we can notice, the proposed method achieves considerable gain (y-axis), with little dependence on the accuracy loss (x-axis), with the latter spanning from 1% to 10%. Instead, the full offloading scheme experiences still considerable gain, but at the cost of dramatically reduced accuracy. This effect is already visible in Figure 2-15(b), which shows the sensitivity of raw data transmission to noise, unlike its counterparts deeper in the architecture.

Figure 2-16: Energy saving with respect to benchmark solutions

Further, Figure 2-17 shows the behaviour of the proposed goal-aware SP selection method, under different channel conditions. The centre figure shows the energy saving as a function of the average path loss. Then, for each point, the corresponding probability mass function of the SP selection is illustrated. As an example, we can notice how the favourable 90 dB path loss allows the end device to offload after a few layers, including transmitting raw data almost 20% of the time. This is because the wireless channel errors do not heavily impact the accuracy, which is constrained to be 88% in this case (the accuracy achieved by the noise-free model is 90%). Instead, increasing the average pathloss, we can notice how the method promotes

deeper local computation, to extract relevant features that are more robust to noise, while avoiding full local computation for the purpose of energy saving. The cost of pushing local computation deeper is a loss in energy saving, as visible from the centre figure. However, even in very harsh channel conditions, the method achieves noticeable gain with respect to Full local computing.

Figure 2-17: Energy saving and corresponding SP selection probability under different channel conditions

To conclude, this section shows an example of how goal-aware neural network splitting at the edge, achieves a very good trade-off between energy, accuracy, latency. The degrees of freedom of SP selection, transmit power and local computing resources allow the method to considerably outperform benchmark solutions such as full local computing and full offloading (i.e., raw data transmission). Future extensions, investigated in WP5 should include multi-user scenarios, as well as a link with the coexistence of semantic, goal-oriented and legacy services.

Conclusions

This section presented three examples of semantic and goal-oriented system optimisation for the edge inference use-case. The proposed solutions involve source and channel coding, as well as system optimisation for workload placement with goal aware DNN splitting. The solutions were briefly described and their potential benefits against classical benchmark schemes. The benefits of the different solutions motivate further investigation to best balance energy, accuracy, computation and communication burden in future wireless networks.

Recommendations for system design

As a general system design requirement, the edge inference use-case needs exchanges of information between layers (e.g., physical layer information) to be able to take the best decision

for workload placement, compression ratio (via either more classical DJSCC schemes or vision transformer-based ones), which also strongly affect energy and latency. As such, as described in Section 3.1, the O1 and E2 interfaces of the S-RIC should be involved for the exchange of performance metrics, collection of SemCom KPIs, and interface between the R-RIS and the Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) platform, which is fundamental to jointly orchestrate wireless and computing resources. The policies described in this section in terms of radio and compute resource allocation should also be fed back by the S-RIC.

2.3 Network Management Use-case

2.3.1 Digital twin with high energy consumption constraint

2.3.1.1 Use-case description

Unlike monitoring systems requiring real time data collecting to make decisions on latest events or system evolution trends, a Digital Twin (DT) modelling function is usually not constraint to such short timeline operation principles. Indeed, a DT function role is mainly to estimate, using model trained on larger timeline periods, the impacts on a system by tuning its parameters before applying them to the real-world. Consequently, larger data collection periods as several minutes can be a satisfying trade-off between energy cost due to this data collection processing for the DT function usage versus the timing requirement to get its model update for next estimates and decisions. In such context, the payload size of the transmitted message and the energy to send a message become the most important criteria over the latency to transmit the information from the observation devices to the DT application.

The DT concept covers many possible applications; the following section covers one specific example to illustrate an energy saving estimate using SemCom to transmit required data from an IoT device to a DT modelling function with a high energy consumption constraint. This example leverages the existing capability of one Low Power and Wide Access transmission mode (LPWA).

Figure 2-18: Data collection using LPWA mode for Digital Twin

This validation example exposes the case of one DT based on a semantic representation of an observed environment thanks to observations collected by cameras scattered throughout the

area of concern. A multitude of IoT devices are capturing images of a real environment for which only a specific semantic area associated with their content are relevant for building its overall semantic representation at DT level. In such cases, instead of sending the full images and transmitting unnecessary information (as in case of representation at pixel level), a semantic encoding can be processed at each device to limit the transmission to the minimum and necessary level of required information. This encoding can be based on a pre-trained model to guarantee a low resource consumption inference. At DT update function side, the received semantic encoded values can be used directly to enrich the environment semantic representation or rendered as images using generative AI.

In this example, we consider a constellation of energy autonomous devices communicating with the DT application using a standard IoT protocol and a LPWA mode at radio link. Such devices are using power harvesting technology to refuel their energy capacity. The usage of such sustainable technology allows relevant cost reductions at deployment and sustaining life cycle steps by requiring no electric cable installation and no manual battery replacement operation.

For such LPWA communications, energy efficiency provided by a SemCom approach is focused on consumption at the User Equipment (UE) side as the main objective of these transmission modes is to save power load to guarantee more autonomy of the IoT device. In case of autonomous power devices using power harvesting technologies (based on solar, heat or vibration sources), applying segmentation to send the observed data periodically is essential to adapt the rate of energy consumed by the radio transmission to the energy refuelling capability of the device.

The power consumption for one message segment should be measured from the first emission on the radio after UE wake-up from its power saving state to its return to sleeping mode. It includes signalling data exchanges, emission of the user data segments, listen on radio link and reception of their acknowledgements at TCP level. It should include also the segment retransmissions in case of no acknowledgement receipt by the UE. In the figure below, message segments are sent at a period of 1 minute with tuned segment size to match with the refuelling capability of the power harvesting technology in use (as example, 1.5 J per minute dedicated to the RF chipset usage).

Figure 2-19: Evolution of Energy capacity and current on LTE-M RF board during message segments transmission

2.3.1.2 Use-case Model

The use-case model consists of assigning semantic labels to every pixel in the input image by an inference running at UE side. This processing uses a pre-trained model originating from mapping a set of images with their semantic representation within the scope of the observed environment. For different profiles of data transmission using different payload sizes the energy

saving on the LTE-M RF board can be estimated in a simple way based on the compression ratio and energy consumption measurement.

Figure 2-20: Data collection using Semantic segmentation for Digital Twin

The energy consumption estimates for one image transmission in usual and more confined conditions (as example an indoor IoT module connected to an LTE-M network antenna with different level of SNRs) can be derived from existing measurement campaigns based rough data payload sizes applied to a 256x256-pixel image sent every 1-minute encoding on different segment sizes (as example, 1 kB, 5kB and full image content size) with and without semantic preprocessing.

2.3.1.3 Results and discussion

The energy consumption impact estimate among the different segment sizes corresponds mainly to the additional signalling cost associated with the wake up of the UE from the sleep mode at each new segment transmission. In case of a poor radio link quality related to the IoT device confinement condition, the additional energy increase is due to the transmission gain increase but also to the segment retransmissions consequent to the appearances of no TCP acknowledgement receipt by the UE.

Basically, the expected improvements adopting a SemCom approach without any change in the existing radio stack and resource management functions are related to the reduced number of message segments sent to carry the fully required information and consequently to the mitigation of retransmission appearances in case of degraded radio conditions. Especially in case of degraded radio conditions, using semantic encoding allows the IoT device to transmit the full image information required by the DT on a single message segment fitting the energy refuelling constraint of the power harvesting technology when it becomes impossible without applying such encoding usage. In such case, this reduces drastically energy consumption and latency in comparison to not using a SemCom approach.

2.3.1.4 Conclusion

At this preliminary estimate stage, the expected energy saving does not consider the energy cost of the semantic encoding inference running on the device which will be addressed on next WP tasks as part of 6G-GOALS project. However, this cost can be mitigated by the usage of pre-trained models restricted to the semantic area covered by the DT and such inference execution is subject of additional optimizations in the scope of the 6G GOALS project. It does not consider also the semantic encoding optimizations and semantic-based radio resources adaptation mechanisms planned as novelties in 6G-GOALS WP 3-4-5.

Next step of the 6G-GOALS project will quantify in a fine-grained manner the estimate of the expected reduction of energy consumption and latency when applying semantic encoding. As exposed in this chapter, these values will be fully applicable in the context of observation data forwarded from an IoT device to a DT update function using a power harvesting technology imposing a high energy consumption constraint.

2.3.1.5 Recommendations for system design

The above use-case requirements, especially the need to adapt data segmentation to the high energy consumption constraint at the device level for LPWA usage should be considered in the system design. For such use case, the introduction of a semantic plane for interaction between the UE and a semantic controller as the Semantic RIC must take into account the limitation in terms of the amount and periodicity of control data to be transmitted to match the energy refuelling capacity of each autonomous device. In case of adopting semantic optimization mechanisms, any task involving control data exchanges and additional processing at the UE side (measures collection, model update, configuration update) must be controlled in term of resource consumption and scheduled following the requirements imposed by the energy capacity constraint.

2.3.2 Semantic state representation

2.3.2.1 Use-case description

Large Language Models (LLMs) underlie nowadays a wide range of applications that, by using human-readable languages, enable simpler and more efficient interaction between a system and the end user. A rapidly expanding research area is the use of LLMs in the management of networking systems, where they are deployed to enhance understanding of the environment and improve network administration without requiring the system operator to know in all detail the low-level network design, configuration, and procedural aspects. This is relevant, for instance, to vertical service administrators that manage their system end to end, who may not be actual experts in mobile networking, and for whom the latter is “just” one of the components that support the whole vertical service, along with other complementary domains (as in content delivery networks, which combine cloud storage systems, transport and multi-technology wireless networks, and an application domain into a single end-to-end service). So, as in [AAC+24], LLMs may be leveraged to define a multi-domain intent handler that translates and decomposes an initial request into infrastructure-level intents to adjust the network state. Validations show that users are indeed highly satisfied with the interaction. Also, LLMs could be easily adapted to multiple downstream tasks. This demonstrates how the power of pre-trained LLMs on general data can be leveraged for specific use-cases by adapting their behaviour introducing intents that provide an advantage not only in interacting through semantic data but also by guiding the system through a goal-oriented behaviour.

Furthermore, LLMs can be exploited to make interoperable heterogeneous systems that a priori do not share a communication protocol and let them “talk” to each other without human mediation. More precisely, thanks to the recent technological advances, the introduction of new machine-to-machine (M2M) communication paradigms [M+24] relies on the fact that devices can exchange data and perform tasks on their own. While this document primarily focuses on human-machine interaction, the proposed approach could also serve as a preliminary step toward exploring LLM-based M2M collaboration. Although this has not yet been implemented, such an extension could potentially further enhance system performance in future developments.

For the specific objectives of the 6G-GOALS project, we consider the need to make large amounts of data related to the 5G core network (5GC) [3GPP23.501] accessible and understandable to users (intended as operators, administrations, maintainers). The latter typically access this information through graphical user interfaces (GUIs), and it is crucial to address the fact that complex network administration operations often require navigating multiple windows, which increases the load and complicates the decision-making process. Furthermore, as the

number of operations grows, critical information is frequently found in logs, which adds to the complexity because users not only need to extract accurate data from diverse sources but also must parse and synthesize large volumes of heterogeneous information. Although experienced users can generally construct a comprehensive view of the network's state after thorough system analysis, the required time and effort increase significantly with task complexity. This highlights the urgent need for tools that streamline information aggregation and simplify data interpretation, leading to more efficient and accurate network management.

Our proposed Semantic State Representation Function (SSRF), defined in [6GGOALS-D21], addresses these challenges directly, and it is also meant to be a preliminary building block towards LLM-supported automated 5GC management and orchestration systems. In combination with advanced ORAN architectures, including the S-RIC that interfaces directly with ORAN APIs and utilizes the semantic communication paradigm, our SSRF has the potential to significantly enhance network efficiency and performance. Although not yet fully realized, by integrating advanced generative AI models like LLMs and state-of-the-art communication techniques, SSRF aims to improve both human-machine interactions and, in the future, M2M communication. This approach could drastically reduce the time required to analyse large datasets and make informed decisions in network management. Moreover, this approach minimizes errors associated with manual processes and enables network operators to focus on strategic tasks instead of routine data management. Overall, the integration of LLMs in network management represents a significant advancement, improving operational efficiency and system reliability while making technology more intuitive for users.

2.3.2.2 Use-case Model

Figure 2-21: SSRF Validation Process.

With the introduction of our SSRF (see also 6G-GOALS's D2.1 [6GGOALS-D21]), we aim to demonstrate that it is possible to leverage pre-trained models to achieve the objective of the described scenario, simplifying the understanding of a large amount of data sourced from the 5GC that is often semantically disconnected. The SSRF is a component that gathers performance, operational, and configuration data from the 5GC system and makes it available in human-readable form to a human user or to a third-party application. Based on this, the SSRF must be capable of i) interacting naturally with the user and ii) providing a response, based on a request about the network status, that is as reliable as possible and meets the specified requirements.

We validated the design and operations of our preliminary version of the SSRF, to assess the effectiveness of the leveraged model. To do so, we tested the SSRF on its capability to address requests that correspond to standard operations typically performed within an information system, namely CRUD operations (Create, Read, Update and Delete), as well as all operations

that can be performed on raw data within the HPE Aruba Networking Private 5GC (HPE 5GC). Namely, we fixed a reference set X of 10 possible network administration actions – See Figure 2-21. These actions include i) information retrieval, ii) information filtering and, finally, iii) mathematical operations over the processed information. Then, with each of the 10 actions of X, labelled as $X = \{SR-0, SR-1, \dots, SR-9\}$ where SR stands for Semantic Request (SR), we associated 100 different but semantically equivalent requests. So, this expanded request set, referred to as Y, contains 1000 phrases in English, each representing different intents that are semantically equivalent to one of the 10 actions of the original set X. Y serves as a validation set used to test the SSRF's ability to correctly interpret and respond to varied input requests.

2.3.2.3 Results and discussion

To validate our proposed SSRF and build X, we identified a set of tasks that cover various possible administration operations within the HPE 5GC. In the end, we obtained a set of requests Y composed of three disjoint subsets: one subset S for “simple actions”, one subset C for “complex actions”, and one subset M for “math operations”, so that $Y = S \cup C \cup M$.

- Set S: this set consists of 400 total sentences associated with 4 actions in X, each corresponding to an information retrieval task from the HPE 5GC or available logs.
- Set C: this set consists of 500 total sentences associated with 5 actions in X, each corresponding to either a comparison between logs and data received from the HPE 5GC or a filtering of data from the HPE 5GC or logs.
- Set M: this set consists of 100 total sentences associated with 1 action in X, in which a mathematical calculation is requested using data received from the core.

We also define the sets SSVR, CSVR, and MSVR as the groups of all semantically valid responses (SVR) for sets S, C, and M, respectively, i.e., the groups of accurate and unambiguous replies obtained when enquiring the SSRF with requests from Y. Furthermore, we define the set of the total semantically valid responses, or more precisely the overall Correct Responses set, as $CR = SSVR \cup CSVR \cup MSVR$, for calculating the SSRF accuracy (A). In our validation test, we forwarded each request in Y to the SSRF exactly once, therefore $0 \leq |CR| \leq |Y|$ and we calculate the overall SSRF accuracy as the ratio between the correct answers CR and the initial set of requests Y. Considering this, for the set S, the goal is to evaluate the ability to extract both structured and unstructured information for general data retrieval processes. For this set, the accuracy for the set of semantically valid response SSVR and aligned with the initial requests S is 74.5% – (average of the four A values in Table 2-2).

Table 2-2: Results of SSVR Validation

Semantic Request	Similar Phrase Tested	Accuracy (A)	90% Request Satisfaction Time
SR-0	100	62%	37s
SR-1	100	71%	35s
SR-2	100	66%	39s
SR-3	100	99%	38s

It is observed that performance decreases when the SSRF works with structured data (see number of SVR for actions SR-0 and SR-2 in Figure 2-22) compared to unstructured data (see number of SVR in SR-1 and SR-3 in Figure 2-22), such as text.

Instead, looking at the bottom part of Figure 2-22 and the values in Table 2-2, for the requests belonging to, 90% of the semantically valid responses (SSRF) are obtained on average within 37.25 seconds. This is a reasonable time considering that for S, the task involves summarizing information from a large amount of both structured and unstructured data.

Figure 2-22: Results of SSVR Validation

Moving to C, the goal is to test the SSRF’s ability to understand context in both structured and unstructured information retrieved using filtering with semantic conditions. For this set, the accuracy for the set of semantically valid response CSVR and aligned with the initial request set C has accuracy around 79% – see Table 2-3. It is worth noting that there is a slight improvement compared to S, for which it was 74.5 %. This is likely due to the increased specificity in the initial requests, helping the SSRF better understand the context and thus increasing its accuracy. Looking more closely at the bottom part of Figure 2-23, we can see that 90% of the responses are obtained on average within 46 seconds – see Table 2-3.

However, this time is mainly influenced by SR-6, which requires filtering operations from both structured and unstructured data simultaneously, thus taking significantly longer than the others. Excluding this semantic request from CSVR set, the average time is about 40 seconds, which is only about 3 seconds longer than for SSVR set, although the complexity of the requests in the latter is lower. Nevertheless, considering the entire CSVR, the SSRF demonstrates its capability to handle large volumes of heterogeneous data, even in more complex operations such as filtering in a reasonable time.

Table 2-3: Results of CSVR Validation

Semantic Request	Similar Phrase Tested	Accuracy (A)	90% Request Satisfaction Time
SR-4	100	68%	35s
SR-5	100	98%	32s
SR-6	100	64%	71s
SR-7	100	84%	36s
SR-8	100	81%	46s

Figure 2-23: Results of CSV Validation

Finally, for the last set M, the SSRF’s ability to understand requests with a mathematical context is tested. The requests in this case are not only designed to retrieve or filter information based on specific contexts but also require arithmetic operations between data of different types. For this set, the accuracy for the set of semantically valid response and aligned with the initial requests (M) is 65% – see Table 2-4. We immediately notice a significant drop in performance of the LLM used for validating the experiments compared to sets SSVR and CSVR.

Table 2-4: Results of MSVR Validation

Semantic Request	Similar Phrase Tested	Accuracy (A)	90% Request Satisfaction Time
SR-9	100	0.65	50s

However, it is worth mentioning that standard LLMs are generally not suited to perform mathematical calculations. Recent models, as seen in recent studies like [YXX+24], are more advanced and can increase accuracy in tasks like those in M. If we look more closely at the bottom part of Figure 2-24 and consider the corresponding values presented in Table 2-4, we can observe that 90% of the requests are satisfied within approximately 50 seconds. When compared to SSVR and CSVR, we observe an average increase of 11 seconds, even though the data needed for these mathematical operations is the same as in the SSVR and CSVR sets. Therefore, the time difference cannot be attributed to the nature or complexity of the data but rather to other factors influencing the processing times, such as the limitations of the LLM in performing mathematical calculations efficiently.

Recalling the initial purpose of this study, which was to assess the SSRF’s capability to adapt to various contexts through retrieval, filtering, and arithmetic operations, Table 2-5 presents a

comprehensive overview of the final accuracy for a selected subset of actions. This subset encompasses both simple and complex actions as well as the entire final action set denoted as CR.

Figure 2-24: Results of MSVR Validation

Despite leveraging the advanced capabilities of the LLM GPT-3.5 [JXN+23], it is essential to acknowledge the inherent limitations faced during this evaluation, including constraints related to token count and other operational factors. The results indicate that the system exhibits a good level of accuracy when managing different requests involving heterogeneous data. A closer examination reveals that requests incorporating arithmetic operations lead to an answer’s correctness drop of nearly 5 %. This decrease in accuracy suggests that while the SSRF demonstrates strong capabilities in many areas, there is a critical need for further enhancements to improve its handling of arithmetic-related requests.

Table 2-5: Results SSRF Validation

SETS	ACCURACY
SSVR ∪ CSVR ∪ MSVR	72 %
SSVR ∪ CSVR	77 %

While specializing LLMs for arithmetic tasks can enhance semantic accuracy, this approach alone is not enough to significantly boost the performance of the SSRF. For instance, integrating a memory mechanism [KYF+23] can greatly improve accuracy by utilizing relevant parts of historical data to inform future interactions, thus enhancing the model’s context-awareness. This

capability allows the SSRF to leverage key information from past queries and responses, resulting in a more tailored user experience. Additionally, the choice of the underlying model is crucial for performance; newer models like GPT-4 [K+23], or recent version like GPT-4-turbo, have been shown to substantially enhance capabilities across linguistic, scientific, and various other fields. This improvement is partly due to GPT-4-turbo's ability to handle a 128k context window, equivalent to processing 300 pages of text in a single prompt, which helps manage complex discussions and provide relevant responses. Furthermore, GPT-4-turbo has a maximum output token limit of 4096, allowing for more detailed answers that are particularly valuable for tasks requiring in-depth analysis. Future evaluations should consider how leveraging this advanced model can enhance the SSRF's overall effectiveness while also addressing the potential increase in energy consumption associated with its use. Furthermore, the assessment of the model should encompass a broader range of metrics beyond simply measuring the number of requests fulfilled accurately and with data aligned to the system's actual data (SA). For example, integrating the Mean Opinion Score (MOS) [JLA+11] can provide valuable insights into user satisfaction and the perceived quality of the responses generated by the SSRF, offering a clearer understanding of the model's performance from the user's perspective.

Despite the challenges and limitations currently faced, it is important to emphasize that the SSRF holds significant potential for future evolution. As we advance toward the creation of an innovative 6G framework, the improvements introduced through the SSRF will play a pivotal role in significantly reducing redundant data processing and transmission. This will streamline operations and ensure the system can manage large volumes of data more effectively, minimizing unnecessary load on the network. Additionally, the SSRF's ability to facilitate semantic and goal-oriented communication will enhance the accuracy and relevance of interactions within the HPE 5GC while supporting also a sustainable network ecosystem.

2.3.2.4 Recommendations for system design

We highlight that the proposed SSRF must be designed to leverage semantic-driven functionalities across the mobile 5G network. From the SSRF's perspective, its interaction with the network relies on well-defined interfaces, exposed and accessed through APIs essential for connecting the SSRF with the underlying mobile infrastructure (e.g., the HPE 5GC and the RAN) and other data sources, such as metric collectors, virtualization layers, and management systems. To enhance its capabilities, the SSRF should also integrate advanced AI techniques, such as LLMs, and employ a federated mechanism with the S-RIC, satisfying the requirements on semantic management loops and semantic AI model lifecycle management described in Section 3. The latter interacts with network elements like the CU/DU to gather performance metrics and contextual information, such as error rates and user mobility. This information can be fed to the SSRF to optimize network operation while maintaining a unified and consistent state. Lastly, the SSRF should expose northbound interfaces to third parties, such as orchestrator, application functions (AFs), or graphical/command-line interfaces for human administrators. This is crucial for enabling interaction with external components beyond the HPE 5GC, ensuring that the network's semantic state can be accessed, updated, and utilized for further management improvements.

2.4 IoT Use-case

In the following, a use-case related to semantic and goal-oriented communications in IoT network is analysed.

2.4.1 Pull-based communication and its coexistence with push-based communication in IoT systems

2.4.1.1 Use-case description

Generally speaking, IoT scenarios considers a high density of devices, such as sensors, deployed to monitor physical quantities of interest, such as environmental conditions or industrial

processes (see also the description of [6GGOALS-D21]). In addition, the IoT traffic in 5G has been largely seen as device-initiated, that is, devices pushing data towards the networks. Recently, the concept of pull-based communication has been considered, in which intelligent nodes (agents) at the network are purposefully pulling data from the IoT devices by sending specific queries and thereby requesting transmissions. This can often be formulated as a *goal-oriented problem* in which the data collection is used for the estimation of a specific process.

In IoT systems, information freshness can be measured through the age of information (AoI). However, for the specific case of pull-based communication, it is more interesting to consider the Query Age of Information (QAoI), which is an extension of AoI that considers the age at instances when there is a request from the destination node. Thus, QAoI penalizes system staleness only when requests are demanded. Optimizing for the QAoI instead of the AoI results in energy savings while keeping the freshness at the important time stamps. The metric was first defined in [HKC+21], and we reproduce two results from the original reference to illustrate its relevance. Figure 2-25 plots the AoI and QAoI in a toy example with a receiver interested in getting updates from a sensor (the transmitter) at given time instants. The time is slotted and each update packet takes one slot. Each update is generated immediately prior to the transmission. The queries Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, \dots arrive periodically, every 7th slot. Furthermore, as an energy constraint, it is assumed that the sender can transmit on average one packet every 3 slots. There are two transmission strategies: the Permanent Query (PQ) in green shows the case in which the sender is oblivious to the query arrival process and distributes the transmissions evenly in time; the Query Arrival Process Aware (QAPA) in orange is a query-driven communication that assumes the sender knows the query instants and optimizes the transmissions with respect to the timing of the query process, i.e., sends just before the query instants. Figure 2-25 shows that the query-driven strategy is more likely to provide updates that are fresh when a query arrives, although its average AoI is worse at the instants in which there is no query.

Figure 2-25: Time evolution of the AoI (solid) and the QAoI (markers) with two transmission strategies: permanent query (PQ) and Query Arrival Process Aware (PAQA) [HKC+21]

Figure 2-26 illustrates the energy savings when optimizing for the queries. Specifically, the energy consumption is modelled with a leaky bucket representing the battery, replenished independently at each step with a probability of 0.2 in this evaluation, and the node can only transmit a packet if there are tokens in the bucket, and each transmission consumes one token. The query happens every 40 slots and packets are lost with a probability 0.2. It is observed that the QAPA strategy accumulates energy when the next query is far in the future, unlike PQ.

The pull-based communication paradigm, together with the development of wake up radios, is able to reduce the energy consumption of IoT nodes. The main radio of the IoT device can be turned off while the wake up radio — a low-cost and low-energy consumption hardware — is listening to specific wake up signals (WuSs). When received, the main radio is turned on and the requested data are transmitted.

Nevertheless, as described in [Sec. 3.4, 6GGOALS-D21], heterogeneous traffic is prone to be considered in 6G IoT networks. Hence, not all devices can operate in pull-based communication

manner, for example due to low-latency requirements or sporadic measurements of the monitored physical quantities. In a realistic environment, it is probable that pull-based communication will be employed side by side to classical push-based communication. Hence, networks will require a Medium Access Control (MAC) layer design enabling the coexistence of the two communication modes (push/pull coexistence), as showcased in the following. Moreover, we present results validating the feasibility of the use-case and analysing the operative behaviour of the system. Further details on this topic can be found in [CSS+24, SCP+24].

Figure 2-26: Available energy tokens over time for two transmission strategies: permanent query (PQ) and Query Arrival Process Aware (PAQA) [HKC+21]

2.4.1.2 Use-case Model

A minimum scenario to test the performance of push/pull coexistence system is considering an IoT setting in which two exclusive subsets of IoT devices employ push- and pull-based communication mode, respectively, and the BS receive queries from a third-party agent (software or hardware) dictating the pulled IoT data. In this evaluation, the intelligent process dictating queries is not investigated. Further investigation on the pulling process decision making will be performed in WP4.

The MAC frame for push/pull coexistence is divided in the pull and push sub-frames, as shown in Figure 2-27. It is worth noting that the relative duration of the pull sub-frame (α) influences the system performance.

Figure 2-27: Toy-example of a MAC frame for push/pull coexistence

2.4.1.3 Results and discussion

The performance evaluation of the systems are discussed in the following.

Figure 2-28 shows the performance evaluation when a Content-based WuS (CoWu) is used (for more details, see [SPC+24]). Specifically, Figure 2-28(a) shows that the optimal relative pull duration (α_{opt}) decreases as the push traffic load λ increases, to satisfy the same push and pull success probability. In Figure 2-28(b), the energy consumption ratio η between push/pull coexistence and a round-robin (RR) scheduling approach is plotted against the push traffic load λ . When pull energy consumption τ_w with CoWu is lower than RR scheduling, $\eta < 1$, indicating an

energy efficiency gain. As λ increases, η rises due to more inter-class collisions and shorter pull relative duration. Push/pull coexistence can outperform RR by up to 38% in pull energy consumption for certain WuS thresholds (V_{th}), while maintaining data accuracy and high push success rates.

2.4.1.4 Recommendations for system design

To integrate push/pull coexistence gaining from the goal-oriented approach of pulling data, future networks should consider the possibility of intelligent nodes to dynamically adapt the frame structure to different traffic requirements, as well as being able to transmit specific WuSs. Moreover, intelligent nodes should have the possibility of estimate the traffic load to make proper decisions about frame structure and the amount of data to pull. Finally, the adoption of wake-up radios hardware for IoT devices should be considered, to have the possibility of reducing device energy consumption.

Figure 2-28: Performance evaluation. (a) optimal relative duration of pull sub-frame (α_{opt}) vs. average push traffic load (λ); (b) energy consumption ratio between push/pull coexistence and pure round-robin (RR) scheduling (η) vs. average push traffic load (λ) [SCP+24].

3 Reference System Design

3.1 6G-GOALS System Architecture

In deliverable [6GGOALS-D21], we provided a taxonomy of system design requirements, categorizing them across architecture, functionality, management and orchestration, integration and compatibility, use-cases, and performance aspects. Each category includes a breakdown of key requirements for the development of the 6G-GOALS system architecture. By defining this taxonomy and by specifying key requirements, we aim to shape the foundational aspects of incorporating semantic and goal-oriented semantic communications in 6G.

This deliverable takes a deeper dive into the earlier introduced concepts for reference system design. We describe they key segments of system design, including the edge, the RAN, and the core network. Through semantic awareness in each segment, we expect significant gains in communication efficiency and energy consumption.

As illustrated in Figure 3-1, for the edge network, we examine SemCom deployments at edge environments. This approach provides numerous benefits, including substantial reductions in data transmission, context-aware task processing, more efficient resource utilization, faster decision-making for edge-centric applications, personalized and adaptive service capabilities, and reduced latency for a broad range of SemCom applications.

At the RAN level, our focus, as presented in [6GGOALS-D21], is on integrating semantic-aware capabilities in the RAN, building on Open RAN architecture and framework. Leveraging SemCom within the RAN enables more efficient spectrum usage and enhances the user experience. Moreover, a semantic-aware RAN can reduce overhead and interference while supporting intelligent reasoning through AI-driven applications and models deployed within this segment.

Finally, the role of the core network in the semantic network is pivotal, where semantic awareness enables a more intelligent approach to managing network operations. By extracting and processing semantic information within the core, we anticipate improvements in traffic management, context-aware quality-of-service adjustments, and an overall service-oriented design. This semantic representation enhances ability of the core network to deliver optimized, intelligent services aligned with user needs and operational goals.

With the pre-defined system design requirements and the network segments outlined above, this deliverable focuses on translating these foundational requirements into specific system design perspectives. This process involves tailoring the broad requirements to address the unique needs and challenges associated with implementing SemCom within a real-world environment.

Given that the ultimate implementation of SemCom centres on semantic applications, we explore the primary bottlenecks and challenges faced during the in-network operation of semantic models. Specifically, we examine how these models interact with critical network resources, influence energy consumption, and necessitate dedicated lifecycle and knowledge base management practices. Addressing these factors is essential to ensuring the sustainable, efficient, and adaptive deployment of SemCom systems across various network segments.

In other EU-funded 6G-centric research projects, AI-native and semantic-aware network design have emerged as central themes. A notable example is the SNS project Hexa-X-II. Its Deliverable D3.3 [HEXAX2-D33] extensively explores topics such as data-driven, modular, and scalable 6G system design; innovative solutions for AI integration, flexible network topologies, and advanced beyond-communication services like sensing and compute offloading; as well as end-to-end system blueprints, AI-driven MLOps and DataOps, semantic-aware communications, cloud transformation, and virtualization.

Among these discussions, the concept of a semantic end-to-end system aligns closely with our work, emphasizing semantic optimization for flexibility and efficiency. It introduces key components such as the semantic deep learning analyser (SDLA) and the semantic edge slicing module (SESM) within the Open RAN architecture for application-level semantic modularity and management.

In 6G-GOALS, we extend some of these ideas by delving into the foundational capabilities of semantic communication, focusing on adaptive L1/L2 mechanisms and comprehensive full-stack end-to-end semantic-aware network design. This deliverable expands several discussion points from [HEXAX2-D33] to advance our semantic network design for 6G-GOALS.

In the following subsections, we begin by briefly reviewing the taxonomy of system design requirements proposed in earlier deliverables. This serves as a foundation for the more detailed discussion that follows, where we introduce and elaborate on the major semantic management loops defined for semantic applications. These loops include: (1) a performance and resource management loop that coordinates semantic model performance with network resource allocation and orchestration, (2) a lifecycle management loop for overseeing the deployment, maintenance, and evolution of semantic models, (3) a knowledge base management loop that supports the organization and retrieval of semantic information, and (4) an energy efficiency management

loop focused on minimizing the power consumption of semantic processes. Together, these management loops form an integrated framework that guides the effective deployment and operation of SemCom applications within the 6G network infrastructure.

Figure 3-1: Major elements and benefits of the 6G-GOALS architecture

3.2 System Design Requirements of 6G-GOALS

In the previous deliverable [6GGOALS-D21], we established the 6G-GOALS system design requirements with a focus on realizing cutting-edge AI-native architectures, alongside semantic and goal-oriented communication paradigms. These requirements were structured into six key areas, each contributing to the comprehensive design of a next-generation communication system.

The **architectural requirements** emphasized the need for semantic understanding and goal orientation, enabling the network to interpret and act on content meaningfully, based on user intents. The architecture was designed to be modular and flexible, facilitating easy integration of different components, while ensuring scalability to handle increased data and maintaining energy-efficient operations. Robustness and adaptability were key factors, ensuring system stability and resilience against uncertainties and changes in the environment.

Functional requirements focused on the essential functionalities needed to support semantic and goal-oriented communication tasks. Context awareness was critical, allowing the network to interpret user intents and adjust communication strategies accordingly. The ability to make decisions at different time scales, including real-time and near-real-time, was a key consideration, alongside managing time-sensitive task processing to maintain causality in multi-sensory inputs. Additionally, distributed reasoning and actuation tasks required collaborative data processing, supported by edge and fog computing for rapid responses.

The **management and orchestration requirements** outlined the coordination needed between new semantic system components and existing legacy network components. The document emphasized the importance of synchronizing and updating the knowledge base to ensure the latest data is available for semantic models. To facilitate the management of these models, a life-cycle management method was introduced, defining how AI models would be trained, monitored, updated, and maintained within the communication system using a new framework called SemComOps.

In terms of **integration and compatibility**, the requirements highlighted the need for seamless co-existence between SemCom components and legacy systems. [6GGOALS-D21] addressed the importance of coordinating task processing capabilities between traditional and semantic processing systems, ensuring that both operate smoothly together without degrading performance.

Semantic-aware 6G-GOALS architecture	Taxonomy of system design requirements	Break down items of system design requirements
6G-GOALS system design requirements	Architectural requirements	Semantic Understanding and Goal Orientation Modularity and Flexibility Scalability and Efficiency Robustness and Adaptability
	Functional requirements	Context Awareness and Semantics Analytics and Decision-Making in Different Time Scales Time-sensitive Task Processing Distributed Reasoning and Actuation Task
	Management & orchestration requirements	Coordination of New System Components and Functions Knowledge Base Synchronization and Updating SemCom Model's Life-cycle Management Method
	Integration and compatibility requirements	Co-existence of SemCom and Legacy Network Components Coordination of Traditional and SemCom Capabilities
	Use-case requirements	Map to four categories of use-cases
	Performance requirements	Performance requirement per use-case Energy efficiency

Figure 3-2: 6G-GOALS system design: requirements, taxonomy, and detailed breakdown

The **use-case requirements** focused on tailoring the system design to specific applications, especially those involving large data exchanges. Performance requirements were divided into classical and semantic KPIs. Classical metrics such as latency, data rate, and reliability were crucial for evaluating the system's fundamental capabilities, while semantic KPIs focused on metrics like the relevance of data and contextual accuracy, ensuring that the system could deliver meaningful information efficiently.

Finally, the **performance requirements** are largely determined by the use-cases. Meanwhile, the energy efficiency requirements also centered on optimizing the system's energy consumption while maintaining communication performance. Strategies such as optimizing semantic coding, resource management, and reducing energy use at the UE level were proposed. The document also stressed the importance of continuously monitoring energy consumption to ensure the overall system achieves a balance between performance and energy efficiency.

These system design requirements provided a structured framework for building a robust, resilient, and goal-oriented 6G communication system capable of supporting future applications with high levels of intelligence and efficiency.

3.3 Semantic Management Loops

In this subsection, we will be focusing on the pillar loops of semantic management over in-network semantic components, modules, and applications. Specifically, the semantic management loops include the semantic-aware resource management and orchestration; semantic AI model lifecycle management, i.e., SemComOps; knowledge base management; and semantic

system energy consumption management. The working mechanisms and major considerations are elaborated in the following.

3.3.1 Semantic-aware resource management and orchestration

Figure 3-3: Goal-oriented and semantic Open RAN of 6G-GOALS

With reference to the 6G-GOALS SemCom-enabled O-RAN architecture [SDS+24] depicted in Figure 3-3, we envision the novel S-RIC entity as an advanced extension of the RAN Intelligent Controller concept within the **Open RAN architecture**. This involves not just the raw data exchange but the interpretation of the data's meaning to enhance network management and optimization. By understanding the context and purpose behind the data, the Semantic-RIC can optimize decision-making processes for various aspects of the network, including energy efficiency and communication goals. This can be achieved by the establishment of novel control-loop involving the main communication actors. The 6G-GOALS architecture extends the O-RAN principles by embedding a deeper understanding of data meaning and communication goals into network management. By collecting comprehensive KPIs from UEs, edge applications, and DU/RU components, the S-RIC can implement context-aware policy changes that optimize network performance. This approach enhances energy efficiency and ensures that the network meets user expectations and application demands, achieving a fine balance between high performance and sustainable operation.

To **collect UE-related Network KPIs**, the Semantic-RIC relies on the E2 interface to receive data indirectly through aggregated or anonymized reports from the CU/DU, which manage interactions with UEs. This data includes performance metrics that help assess how well transmitted data matches its intended meaning upon reception, along with semantic error rates that

indicate discrepancies in comprehension. Additionally, the RIC gathers contextual data related to the environment, such as user location and movement, enabling more refined real-time network optimizations. For broader performance data that may include network-wide KPIs and fault management, the S-RIC can use the **O1 interface** to interact with the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework. The SMO collects and processes data from various network elements, aggregating it into reports that the S-RIC can access for deeper analysis.

While the S-RIC may not have direct access to application-specific data from within UEs, it can infer semantic-related insights through reports generated by network analytics tools that observe traffic patterns and application behaviour. These tools can highlight discrepancies between sent and received data or identify high semantic error rates, which the S-RIC can act on. To **collect UE-related SemCom KPIs**, the S-RIC can work with APIs and data aggregation tools from edge computing platforms. While direct interaction between the Semantic-RIC and the UE is not standard, potential future implementations may explore more direct data collection methods and are currently under considerations.

In terms of **application KPIs**, the S-RIC interfaces with applications at the edge through integrated MEC platforms, when the ETSI standard is adopted for edge infrastructure deployment. These interactions provide valuable insights such as latency and throughput need, which are crucial for understanding how application performance correlates with network behaviour. Additionally, quality of experience (QoE) feedback from applications helps the RIC evaluate user satisfaction levels, while energy consumption metrics contribute to its energy-saving strategies. This data enables the S-RIC to prioritize and adapt resource allocation based on the unique requirements of each application.

The **collection of network KPIs from DU/RU** components is facilitated through the O1 and E2 interfaces. The RIC extracts detailed information on the wireless signal quality, such as signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and channel state, along with utilization data that reveals how network load is distributed across different nodes. These metrics are essential for identifying areas of high traffic and implementing load-balancing measures. Energy usage statistics from the DU and RU are particularly important for the RIC's energy optimization efforts, providing a real-time view of power consumption across different network layers. Once KPIs are gathered, the **S-RIC feeds back policy changes and adjustments** to the RAN to improve network performance and energy efficiency. These adjustments might involve dynamic changes in resource allocation, such as modifying power levels, frequency usage, and scheduling strategies, to align with real-time traffic demands and communication goals. The RIC's semantic focus allows it to prioritize data transmission based on importance and context, ensuring that critical data (e.g., emergency IoT updates) is given priority over less essential traffic. ML algorithms can be integrated into the S-RIC to enhance its decision-making capabilities. These models help predict optimal network configurations based on historical data, enabling the RIC to proactively adjust to changing conditions. This predictive power allows for smarter scheduling and resource allocation that aligns with both real-time KPIs and the overarching communication objectives.

The S-RIC's awareness of communication goals ensures that it can adjust network policies in a context-sensitive manner. For instance, when handling video streaming, which demands minimal semantic distortion, the RIC may implement policies that enhance data fidelity and reduce latency. For applications that can tolerate higher semantic loss but require reliability, such as certain IoT data transmissions, the RIC may implement energy-saving protocols that optimize power consumption while maintaining data comprehension.

Feedback loops are essential for the S-RIC to refine its strategies continuously. By comparing collected KPIs with desired network states, it can evaluate the effectiveness of its policy changes and adapt them accordingly. This process includes modifying **Layer 1 and Layer 2 (L1/L2) controls**, such as adjusting MCS, to ensure efficient use of resources while preserving the semantic integrity of transmitted data. The S-RIC can issue commands that prompt DUs and RUs to enter energy-saving modes or reduce transmission power during periods of low

traffic, thus balancing the overall network performance with energy-saving and sustainability goals, adapting to end-users traffic demand and mobility.

3.3.2 Semantic AI model lifecycle management (SemComOps).

3.3.2.1 SemComOps Principle

Semantic communication operations (**SemComOps**) share common principles with machine learning operations (MLOps) for managing machine learning-based systems, but the key differences stem from their distinct applications and the unique challenges of SemCom, especially for the implementation of SemCom models in 6G. In principle, the key differences are listed as follows:

Table 3-1: SemComOps vs MLOps

Aspect	MLOps	SemComOps	Why This Difference Matters
Data Representation	Focuses on traditional feature vectors, images, or text	Involves high-level semantic meanings (concepts, goals, context)	Semantic communication relies on extracting and encoding meaning beyond raw data, so it must consider context-aware information.
Model Deployment	Primarily manages model lifecycle for prediction tasks	Involves deployment of semantic encoder/decoder models for real-time communication	The operational focus shifts to ensuring real-time performance, goal achievement, and context preservation in transmission.
Pipeline Complexity	Predominantly deals with training, tuning, and monitoring ML models	Needs additional layers for semantic extraction, meaning refinement, and feedback mechanisms	Semantic communication requires feedback from receivers to enhance or adjust meanings.
Performance Metrics	Accuracy, precision, recall, F1, etc.	Goal achievement, semantic fidelity, intent satisfaction, and other semantic-centric metrics	Unlike typical MLOps, SemComOps is concerned with how well the transmitted information achieves a specific goal or understanding.
Feedback Mechanisms	Monitoring model performance (accuracy, latency)	Monitoring model performance, feedback from user equipment (UE) for goal-oriented communication	Monitoring model performance is one aspect. Meanwhile, feedback loops from users help refine semantic interpretations for improving communication reliability and performance.

3.3.2.2 Pipeline Design for 6G-GOALS In-Network SemComOps

To design a pipeline for in-network SemComOps, it must handle semantic extraction, communication, and feedback adaptation in a real-time, distributed manner. We give an overall pipeline structure as follows.

Task Specification: The process begins with defining the specific communication task. This step is critical as it sets the context and goals for the semantic communication process. The task may involve goal-oriented communication, such as transmitting key meanings or achieving intent-driven actions.

Data Collection: Once the task is specified, the next step involves collecting relevant data from UE or network edge devices or existing public dataset. The data collected at this stage includes raw data that will be transformed into semantically meaningful information.

Knowledge Base Creation: After data collection, the system constructs a Knowledge Base. This knowledge base contains domain-specific information, patterns, and context that guide the semantic encoding and decoding processes. It plays a key role in enhancing the semantic fidelity and goal achievement of the communication.

Semantic Encoder/Decoder Training: With the knowledge base in place, the semantic encoder and decoder models are trained. These models learn to extract semantic features from the data (encoder) and interpret those features (decoder) to recover the meaning. The training process typically uses data labelled with relevant semantic information.

Semantic Encoder/Decoder Deployment: After training, the encoder/decoder models are deployed in the network infrastructure (at the edge and RAN) or directly on UE devices. This deployment is essential for facilitating real-time communication in the network or between devices.

Monitoring Mechanism: A critical component of the pipeline is a monitoring mechanism. This system tracks the performance of the deployed semantic encoder and decoder models, assessing their ability to achieve communication goals (e.g., meaning extraction, intent satisfaction) and ensuring real-time adaptation when necessary.

Figure 3-4: An overview of the SemComOps pipeline

UE Feedback Collection: For models deployed on UE, feedback is continuously collected from the UE side. This feedback includes information about the success of the communication, such as whether the transmitted meaning aligns with the intended goal or how well the system has adapted to varying conditions.

Dynamic Adjustment (Model/Knowledge Base): Based on the monitoring system and feedback from UE, dynamic adjustments can be made to either the semantic encoder/decoder models or the knowledge base itself. These adjustments improve the system's ability to handle evolving semantic communication needs, ensuring ongoing efficiency and accuracy in real-time communication scenarios.

By including these steps in the pipeline, the system ensures that semantic communication is highly adaptive, goal-oriented, and capable of learning and improving over time with user feedback. This process supports real-time, low-latency, and context-aware communication in 6G networks.

3.3.3 Knowledge base management

In SemCom, knowledge base management emerges as a pivotal component, acting as the backbone that enables semantic models to function effectively and improve over time. It serves as a dynamic loop that aligns the training datasets (knowledge) of semantic ML models with the execution domain knowledge, ensuring that the models remain relevant and effective across different applications and over time.

Knowledge base management in semantic communications involves more than just storing and retrieving information. It is about the systematic curation, updating, and utilization of knowledge that the semantic models rely on to interpret and generate meaningful communication. This management process includes:

1. **Knowledge Acquisition:** Collecting data from various sources, including network operation, user interactions, environmental sensors, and external databases.
2. **Knowledge Representation:** Structuring this data into formats that are accessible and interpretable by machine learning algorithms.
3. **Knowledge Updating:** Continuously refining the knowledge base to incorporate new information and discard obsolete data, ensuring the semantic models adapt to changes in the environment and user needs.
4. **Knowledge Distribution:** Effectively disseminating the updated knowledge across different network segments to maintain consistency and coherence in semantic understanding.

By meticulously managing the knowledge base, SemCom systems can enhance their ability to comprehend context, predict user needs, and deliver more personalized and efficient communication services.

Understanding that different network segments have varying requirements and constraints, it is crucial to tailor knowledge bases accordingly. In the 6G-GOALS framework, we define a distributed knowledge base (DKB) system that comprises the global knowledge base (GKB), access knowledge base (AKB), local knowledge base (LKB), and user knowledge base (UKB). These knowledge bases are designed to align with the generic architecture of wireless networks. Below is an elaboration of the main functionalities of each knowledge base, presented in paragraphs for enhanced readability.

The **GKB** is a centralized knowledge repository located at the cloud data centre. It contains comprehensive, aggregated semantic information accessible across the entire network. Acting as the master source of semantic information, the GKB integrates data from various regional, local, and user knowledge bases. It holds universal knowledge that supports inference, reasoning, and learning across different regions and users. The GKB facilitates global tasks such as

large-scale semantic analysis, policy setting, and high-level decision-making. It is responsible for aggregating and storing knowledge from all connected knowledge bases in the network. Additionally, the GKB assists with high-level semantic tasks like model training and distributes updates and high-level insights to regional and local knowledge bases.

The **AKB** is a region-specific knowledge repository residing at the same level of hierarchy as an edge server. It manages knowledge specific to a geographic area, a set of connected BSs, or core network functions distributed at the edge. The AKB handles regional semantic information and performs mid-level tasks that benefit from low-latency edge processing, such as real-time optimization, network load balancing, and interference management within a specific region. AKBs translate global policies from the GKB into regional adjustments and coordinate semantic tasks across multiple BSs optimize QoS and resource allocation. They also aggregate data from LKBs and provide feedback to the GKB.

The **LKB** is a localized knowledge repository situated at BS-level. It provides cell-specific knowledge and supports low-latency, immediate-response tasks. LKBs perform local optimizations, user scheduling, and resource allocation within a specific cell or coverage area. They handle knowledge directly related to connected devices and adapt quickly to changing network conditions. The LKB manages user-specific information and real-time semantic tasks, such as adapting transmission parameters based on user profiles and channel conditions. Additionally, LKBs collect usage patterns and quality metrics to inform local adjustments and send this data back to the AKB. They are responsible for executing rapid semantic inference or content caching for frequently accessed data.

The **UKB** is an individual knowledge repository located on the user equipment, such as smartphones or IoT devices. It holds user-specific semantic information based on individual preferences, history, and usage patterns, which can vary due to differences in knowledge levels. The UKB allows for personalized, user-centric semantic processing directly at the device level, supporting ultra-low latency for applications like content recommendation, personalized caching, and real-time adaptation to user preferences. One of its functionalities is storing user-specific data, such as personal preferences, usage history, and localized content. It adapts content and service quality based on device conditions like battery level and network connectivity. Additionally, UKBs provide personalized feedback to LKBs, supporting device-specific adjustments and enabling predictive caching and content recommendations.

Figure 3-5: Illustration of the DKB system and its key component.

Overall, the proposed DKB system in 6G-GOALS is designed to optimize SemCom by aligning knowledge management with the wireless network architecture. By structuring the knowledge bases in this hierarchical and distributed manner, the system ensures efficient, low-latency, and

context-aware communication across the entire network, catering to both global objectives and individual user preferences.

3.3.4 Semantic system energy consumption management

The introduction of an energy consumption management applied to a semantic radio network system can be addressed at different levels based on semantic information and radio operation state awareness by the SemCom control functions with specific energy impacts on the different network subsystems.

Following aspects must be considered when defining the SemCom system architecture with different impacts on the overall system energy consumption:

- Real time versus near or non-real time processing applied to energy consumption management and optimization.
- Types of network entities on which energy management and optimization is applied (SemCom modules, RAN entities, etc.)
- Usage of short, near or long observation periods by the decision models with energy management and optimization objectives.
- Level of Radio awareness by the semantic and energy controller functions.
- Direct or indirect energy impact caused by the energy management and optimization processing on different communication system components (UE, energy-centric 3rd-party apps, RAN).
Capability to management energy efficiency level agreements or energy consumption quotas at the required level of communication granularity and layer.
- Extended capability of energy management to the core network.

Based on the targeted capabilities and impacts as listed above, the energy consumption of a SemCom system can be managed in local entities (UE, user application) without control plane usage or by a control entity at application function, Radio Access or Network Management level through such control framework.

4 Discussion

This deliverable presents the final results of the reference system, scenarios, use-case analysis, and requirements for the 6G-GOALS project. Through the validation of the selected use-cases, we have demonstrated the benefits of adopting SemCom across diverse applications, particularly in terms of communication efficiency and energy conservation. The reference architecture design outlined herein transitions the system design from abstract requirements to tangible semantic management loops. These foundational activities set the stage for more detailed architecture development. In this section, we discuss potential research directions and topics that could enhance the system architecture design.

4.1 Completeness of Semantic Management Loops

The integration of SemCom models as applications embedded within the network infrastructure necessitates additional efforts for their control and management. Unlike traditional communication systems, SemCom deals with the transmission of meaning rather than raw data, which introduces new complexities in ensuring accurate semantic interpretation across network nodes. Effective management of these semantic processes is crucial to maintain the integrity and efficiency of communication. That's the fundamental reason for us to raise 4 critical semantic management loops in this deliverable. These loops involve continuous monitoring, adaptation, and optimization of semantic encoding and decoding processes in response to changing network conditions, user requirements, energy consumption and environmental factors. By incorporating feedback mechanisms, semantic management loops enable the system to learn

from past communications, adjust strategies in real-time, and improve overall performance. Implementing and validating these semantic management loops in the future is essential for the dynamic operation of SemCom systems.

For large-scale deployments, further investigation into management loops is required to address scalability challenges. In expansive networks, semantic resources must be allocated efficiently among numerous nodes, which may have competed or cooperative interactions. Developing robust strategies for semantic resource allocation—whether through competitive algorithms that optimize individual node performance or cooperative approaches that enhance overall network efficiency—is vital for the successful implementation of SemCom in real-world scenarios.

Moreover, the evolving research and new functionalities emerging from other WPs within the 6G-GOALS project can enrich these semantic management loops. Integrating interdisciplinary insights and innovations can lead to more sophisticated management mechanisms, enhancing the adaptability and resilience of the semantic network architecture.

4.2 Synergies of GAI and SemCom at the Architecture Level

Generative AI (GAI) has emerged as a transformative technology, capable of producing rich, context-aware content such as text, images, and videos based on input prompts. Its inherent ability to interpret and generate complex data aligns seamlessly with the semantic and goal-oriented communication paradigms emphasized in the 6G-GOALS architecture. This section explores how GAI can enhance SemCom while supporting the foundational principles of 6G-GOALS.

GAI for SemCom in the 6G-GOALS Architecture

In the 6G-GOALS modular architecture, GAI can play a pivotal role as both the encoder and decoder within the SemCom framework:

- **Semantic Encoding and Decoding:** GAI's capability to compress multimodal content (text, images, videos) into compact, semantically meaningful representations aligns with semantic awareness and efficiency requirements of 6G-GOALS. By minimizing transmitted data while preserving high-fidelity semantics, GAI reduces bandwidth consumption, addressing the scalability and efficiency goals for edge-centric deployment.
- **Dynamic Knowledge Adaptation:** The ability of GAI to serve as a dynamic knowledge base enables real-time semantic alignment between the sender and receiver. This supports the adaptability and goal orientation principles of 6G-GOALS by ensuring both parties operate with a shared semantic frame of reference, improving robustness and accuracy in dynamic network environments. Further, GAI-processed the dynamic knowledge base can be efficiently exposed to network administrators and orchestrators.
- **Enhanced Real-time Interactions:** For 6G applications such as immersive experiences and autonomous systems, GAI's high-speed reconstruction of semantic information directly addresses the low-latency and real-time interaction goals of 6G-GOALS.

SemCom for GAI in the 6G-GOALS Context

While GAI enhances SemCom, the reverse relationship, SemCom enhancing GAI, is equally important within the 6G-GOALS distributed and resource-efficient architecture:

- **Distributed AI Systems:** By leveraging SemCom's principles of efficient semantic transmission, GAI-based systems can operate more effectively in distributed environments such as federated learning or multi-agent collaborative systems. This supports the modularity and resource efficiency goals of 6G-GOALS, particularly in bandwidth-constrained scenarios.

- **Optimized Communication Overhead:** Applying SemCom’s data compression strategies to GAI models reduces redundancy in distributed learning and inference. This ensures that semantic fidelity is preserved while minimizing communication overhead, directly contributing to energy efficiency and sustainability, which are critical for 6G-GOALS.
- **Robustness in Collaborative Learning:** In 6G-enabled collaborative AI deployments, GAI systems enhanced by SemCom can maintain semantic consistency and robustness, ensuring that critical information is preserved despite network disruptions or adversarial conditions. This supports goal orientation and contextual reasoning within the architecture.

In summary, by embedding Generative AI into the 6G-GOALS semantic-aware architecture, and utilizing Semantic Communication to optimize GAI applications, we create a synergistic system capable of achieving unparalleled levels of intelligence, efficiency, and adaptability. This integration not only accelerates innovation in 6G-enabled applications but also fulfils the core objectives of the 6G-GOALS framework. Future research should focus on refining these synergies, with an emphasis on addressing architectural challenges and deployment scalability.

5 Conclusion

This deliverable extends the foundational work of [6GGOALS-D21] and [6GGOALS-D22], and provides the final results of 6G-GOALS for scenarios, use-cases, and reference system design. Through simulation results for multimedia-centric, task-oriented, network management, and IoT use-case categories, it demonstrates the practicality and advantages of semantic communication in real-world scenarios, highlighting its potential to revolutionize wireless networks with AI-driven, agile, and knowledge-centric architectures. The deliverable delves into the reference system architecture, covering semantic-aware RAN, edge, and core network elements, while emphasizing four key semantic management loops: performance monitoring, resource allocation and orchestration, model lifecycle oversight, and energy optimization. It also refines system design criteria based on earlier identified requirements, and introduces actionable insights for practical system implementation such knowledge base management. Furthermore, this deliverable lays the foundation for the detailed 6G-GOALS system architecture design, which will be covered in future deliverables of WP2. The insights provided here not only advance the current understanding of semantic communications but also guide the activities of other WPs.

6 References

- [3GPP23.501] 3GPP, “System architecture for the 5G System (5GS)”, 3GPP23.501.
- [3GPP38.901] 3GPP, "Study on channel model for frequencies from 0.5 to 100 GHz (Release 14)," 3GPP TR 38.901 V14.0.0, Mar. 2017, [Online]. Available: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3173>
- [6GGOALS-D21] Deliverable D2.1 from HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-GOALS.
- [6GGOALS-D22] Deliverable D2.2 from HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-GOALS.
- [AAC+24] Abdelkader Mekrache; Adlen Ksentini; Christos Verikoukis, “Intent-Based Management of Next-Generation Networks: an LLM-Centric Approach”, IEEE Network (Volume: 38, Issue: 5, September 2024).

- [AA+24] Abdelkader Mekrache; Adlen Ksentini, "LLM-enabled Intent-driven Service Configuration for Next Generation Networks", 2024 IEEE 10th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 10 July 2024.
- [A98] S. M. Alamouti, "A simple transmit diversity technique for wireless communications," in IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, vol. 16, no. 8, pp. 1451-1458, Oct. 1998, doi: 10.1109/49.730453.
- [Ban19] P. Bansal, "Intel image classification: Image scene classification of multiclass," 2019.
- [BBG19] E. Bourtsoulatze, D. Burth Kurka and D. Gündüz, "Deep Joint Source-Channel Coding for Wireless Image Transmission," in IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 567-579, Sept. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TCCN.2019.2919300.
- [BMB+24] F. Binucci, M. Merluzzi, P. Banelli, E. C. Strinati and P. Di Lorenzo, "Enabling Edge Artificial Intelligence via Goal-oriented Deep Neural Network Splitting," 2024 19th International Symposium on Wireless Communication Systems (ISWCS), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 2024, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ISWCS61526.2024.10639178.
- [CSS+24] Cavallero, S., Saggese, F., Shiraishi, J., Pandey, S. R., Buratti, C., & Popovski, P. "Coexistence of Pull and Push Communication in Wireless Access for IoT Devices." Accepted in SPAWC 2024, arXiv preprint at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.07650>.
- [CSW+23] C. Bian, Y. Shao, H. Wu and D. Gündüz, "Space-Time Design for Deep Joint Source Channel Coding of Images over MIMO Channels," 2023 IEEE 24th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC), Shanghai, China, 2023, pp. 616-620, doi: 10.1109/SPAWC53906.2023.10304536.
- [DPP+24] A. Devoto, S. Petruzzi, J. Pomponi, P. Di Lorenzo, S. Scardapane, "Adaptive Semantic Token Selection for AI-native Goal-oriented Communications," in proc. of IEEE SPAWC 2024.
- [EKG+19] E. Bourtsoulatze, D. Burth Kurka and D. Gündüz, "Deep Joint Source-Channel Coding for Wireless Image Transmission," in IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 567-579, Sept. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TCCN.2019.2919300.
- [GWT+24] D. Gündüz, M. A. Wigger, T. -Y. Tung, P. Zhang and Y. Xiao, "Joint Source-Channel Coding: Fundamentals and Recent Progress in Practical Designs," in Proceedings of the IEEE, 2024, doi: 10.1109/JPROC.2024.3477331.
- [GY22] J. Guo and C. Yang, "Learning Precoding for Semantic Communications," 2022 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops), Seoul, Korea, Republic of, 2022, pp. 163-168, doi: 10.1109/ICCWorkshops53468.2022.9814464.
- [HEXAX2-D33] Hexa-X-II "Deliverable D3.3 - Initial analysis of architectural enablers and framework," Apr. 2024.
- [HKC+21] Holm, J, Kalør, A. E., Chiariotti, F. Soret, B. Jensen, S. K. Pedersen, T. B. & Popovski, P., "Freshness on Demand: Optimizing Age of Information for

- the Query Process," ICC 2021 - IEEE International Conference on Communications, Montreal, QC, Canada, 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICC42927.2021.9500894.
- [HNB+68] P. E. Hart, N. J. Nilsson, and B. Raphael, "A formal basis for the heuristic determination of minimum cost paths," IEEE Transactions on Systems Science and Cybernetics, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 100–107, 1968.
- [JLA+11] Jie Xu; Liyuan Xing; Andrew Perkis, et al., "On the Properties of Mean Opinion Scores for Quality of Experience Management," 2011 IEEE International Symposium on Multimedia, 09 January 2012.
- [JXN+23] Junjie Ye, Xuanting Chen, Nuo Xu, et al., "A Comprehensive Capability Analysis of GPT-3 and GPT-3.5 Series Models," arXiv:2303.10420 [cs.CL].
- [KYF+23] Kai Zhang, Yangyang Kang, Fubang Zhao, Xiaozhong Liu, "LLM-based Medical Assistant Personalization with Short- and Long-Term Memory Coordination," arXiv:2309.11696 [cs.CL].
- [K+23] Koubaa, Anis., "GPT-4 vs. GPT-3.5: A Concise Showdown," 10.36227/techrxiv.22312330.v2.
- [LMA+23] I. Labriji, M. Merluzzi, F. E. Airod and E. C. Strinati, "Energy-Efficient Cooperative Inference Via Adaptive Deep Neural Network Splitting at the Edge," ICC 2023 - IEEE International Conference on Communications, Rome, Italy, 2023, pp. 1712-1717, doi: 10.1109/ICC45041.2023.10279444.
- [M+24] Islam, Md Samiul, "Machine-to-Machine Communication in Industry 4.0: A Digital Transformation," 10.13140/RG.2.2.12672.24327.
- [MBR+23] M. Merluzzi et al., "The Hexa-X Project Vision on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning-Driven Communication and Computation Co-Design for 6G," in IEEE Access, vol. 11, pp. 65620-65648, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3287939.
- [MFG+24] Merluzzi, M.; Filippou, M.C.; Gomes Baltar, L.; Mueck, M.D.; Calvanese Strinati, E. "6G Goal-Oriented Communications: How to Coexist with Legacy Systems?" Telecom 2024, 5, 65-97. <https://doi.org/10.3390/telecom5010005>.
- [PKC+24] J. Park, S. -W. Ko, J. Choi, S. -L. Kim, J. Choi and M. Bennis, "Towards Semantic MAC Protocols for 6G: From Protocol Learning to Language-Oriented Approaches," in IEEE BITS the Information Theory Magazine, 2024, doi: 10.1109/MBITS.2024.3491949.
- [SCP+24] Shiraishi, J., Cavallero, S., Pandey, S. R., Saggese, F., Popovski, P. "Co-existence of Push Wireless Access with Pull Communication for Content-based Wake-up Radios." Accepted to GLOBECOM 2024, arXiv preprint at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.12816>.
- [SHZ18] Sandler, Mark, et al. "Mobilenetv2: Inverted residuals and linear bottlenecks." Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer
- [SDS+24] E. C. Strinati, P. Di Lorenzo, V. Sciancalepore, et al., "Goal-Oriented and Semantic Communication in 6G AI-Native Networks: The 6G-GOALS Approach," in 2024 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit), 2024, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597087.

- [WWG+23] W. F. Lo, N. Mital, H. Wu and D. Gündüz, "Collaborative Semantic Communication for Edge Inference," in *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 1125-1129, July 2023, doi: 10.1109/LWC.2023.3256006.
- [YXX+24] Yifan Xu, Xiao Liu, Xinghan Liu et al., "ChatGLM-Math: Improving Math Problem-Solving in Large Language Models with a Self-Critique Pipeline", arXiv:2404.02893 [cs.CL]
- [ZWL+23] H. Zhang, H. Wang, Y. Li, K. Long and V. C. M. Leung, "Toward Intelligent Resource Allocation on Task-Oriented Semantic Communication," in *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 70-77, June 2023, doi: 10.1109/MWC.008.2200504.